

**A STRATEGIC AND OPERATIONAL ANALYSIS OF
DELIVERING SCIENCE LESSONS IN SECURE
CHILDREN'S HOMES ACROSS ENGLAND AND WALES**

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Preface

This is an adapted public version of the dissertation. It has been edited to protect participant anonymity and remove personal details, in line with BERA ethical guidelines. All findings and recommendations remain intact, and the document is provided for dissemination to practitioners, researchers and policy-makers in youth justice and education.

Abstract

This dissertation examines how science education is delivered to young people in Local Authority Secure Children's Homes (LASCHs) in England and Wales. It situates the research within the historical, political and socio-economic context of the secure estate and identifies challenges that shape educational provision. A case study methodology was employed, using questionnaires and structured interviews with Heads of Education and science teachers.

Findings highlight systemic barriers including lack of baseline assessment, inconsistent identification of special educational needs, resource limitations, and pressures created by short custodial stays. Science teachers reported additional challenges such as teaching learners with low literacy levels, restricted access to practical laboratories, and managing complex behaviour.

The study contributes to the limited body of research on education in secure children's homes and proposes recommendations to strengthen assessment, SEN provision, staff training, curriculum design, behaviour management, and cross-agency information sharing.

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1.0 Introduction

This introductory section explains the research focus and rationale behind my decision to research the delivery of science to young offenders in Local Authority Secure Children's Homes (LASCHs). It details the aim of the project with the underlying objectives and questions that needed to be answered to meet that aim.

1.1 Research focus

This research project was in two parts. The initial part of the research was to understand the differences between the LASCH and their education departments. Once the data on the different LASCH and education departments had been collected, telephone interviews were conducted with the science teachers as the timeline in table 1 shows.

Table 1: Timeline of Research Project

March 2014	April 2014	May 2014	June 2014	July 2014	August 2014
Gain permission for project. Create and trial questionnaire for Heads of Education.		Discussion at Heads of Education meeting to agree content of questionnaire	Edit and issue questionnaire to Heads of Education.	Collect in returns before the end of term	Analyses and collation of data from Heads of Education.
September 2014	October 2014	November 2014	December 2014	January - March 2015	
Analyses and collation of data from Heads of Education.	Create and trial structured interview questions for science teachers..	Carry out telephone interviews with science teachers	Analyses and collation of data from science teachers	Write and submit research.	

The basis of the project was to understand how the science teachers managed their lessons to generate a picture of best practice that could be shared.

The initial part of the research was quite broad in terms of identifying and understanding the operational differences between the units and the education departments. It then narrowed to understanding the delivery of science. It did not attempt to look at how the National Curriculum for science is delivered or suggest

ways to address gaps in science attainment, partly because there are changes on the horizon for GCSE science and partly because if it was successful then the attainment gap would be addressed.

1.2 Research Rationale

This research was prompted by my previous research (Chellew, 2013) which investigated whether an induction programme could re-engage disaffected pupils in science. To move my previous research forward I needed to know if the other science teachers were experiencing the same level of anxiety from the pupils and were finding teaching challenging given all the barriers in place.

A collaborative project was not going to be easy, not just because of the logistics around geographical locations, the competition for funding from the Youth Justice Board (YJB) and the lack of time that all teachers suffer from, but also because it required a change in culture as this would be the first collaborative project of this kind. I did not know how a collaborative project would be received at a management level, plus the success of this project would depend on teachers being honest and possibly exposed and vulnerable. For this project to be a success, I needed the security in the form of confidentiality and anonymity provided by an academic research project overseen by a university.

The timing of this project was fortuitous as it started at the same time as the number of beds bought by the YJB, as a result of the 2013 Spending Review, was announced. Staff would hopefully feel more secure about sharing information as the units were not competing for beds from the YJB. This, along with the fact that there is a drive to reduce the number of young people being put in secure accommodation with a consequential reduction in funding, meant that a project looking at identifying and sharing best practice could potentially increase the cost effectiveness for education.

Discussions with the Head of Education (HoE) highlighted that there was not a clear picture of how each LASCH operated, what subjects were taught or the number and type of beds (see context below). Before I could identify and share best practice, I needed to get a clear picture of each LASCH to understand if best practice could be shared.

1.3 Research Aims and Questions

The aim of this project was to identify best practice in teaching science in LASCHs. In order to meet this aim the following objectives would need to be met:

1. To understand the difference between the LASCHs.

This meant asking questions about;

- a. The number and type of beds (YJB or Welfare),
- b. Resources (budgets and staffing),
- c. Information on young persons (YPs).

2. To understand the differences between the education departments.

This meant asking questions about;

- a. Curriculum delivered,
- b. Staff qualifications and training,
- c. Assessment of YPs.

3. To identify current practice in science teaching.

This meant asking questions on;

- a. the use of practicals,
- b. literacy and numeracy,
- c. Special Educational Needs (SEN) including emotional, social, behavioural disorders (ESBD),
- d. Qualifications delivered.

1.4 Structure of the Dissertation

Section 2 gives a personal overview, an explanation on the different types of secure accommodations available and a more detailed locational context. The historical and political contexts are also discussed.

Section 3 discusses the current thinking about education for young offenders and extrapolates from ideas from other areas such as teaching in Pupil Referral Units (PRUs).

Section 4 looks at the benefits and limitations of the methodology and the underpinning methods.

Section 5 analysis the data received from questionnaires and interviews that impact on the delivery of science.

Section 6 details the conclusions of the project bringing together the literature review and data analysis to put forward the recommendations from this project.

2.0 Contextualisation

This research is based on how science lessons are delivered in LASCHs. This section provides background information as this setting is very different to other educational contexts where research could be done. It gives the project wider context by considering the political, socio-economic, legislative and other factors which condition the environment in which LASCHs operate. Finally, this section includes a brief autobiography to give an insight into how I view my work, this project and why this research is important to me.

2.1 LASCHs

2.1.1 Demographic context

Currently, there are three types of secure centres for young offenders under the age of 18. Broadly speaking, the youngest are detained in LASCHs (these can be as young as 10), slightly older in secure training centres (STCs) and the oldest in young offenders' institutions (YOIs) (usually no younger than 15 years old). (House of Commons, 2013, p.38)

A secure children's home houses some of the most 'extremely vulnerable children with most complex and challenging needs' (Ofsted, 2012, p.6) who may be 'detained either on the grounds of their offending or for their welfare' (Stephenson, 2007, p.23). Therefore, they may be or have one or a combination of the following;

- young offenders,
- victims of abuse,
- learning difficulties,
- mental health issues,
- had a disrupted education.

It is important to remember that the young offenders are just children who feel, and probably are, neglected and forgotten by society. As Hayden (2008, p.31) says ‘these kids are everybody’s and nobody’s problem’ and given that they are children, near the start of their lives, they require a holistic approach to their rehabilitation, of which education is a subset and science is part of that education.

At the start of this project there were 17 LASCHs with a good geographical spread across England and Wales (see appendix 1). They had the capacity to take 298 offenders and welfare children aged between 10 and 17, who could come from anywhere within Britain and can stay for between one night and many years. Table 2 (DfE 2014, no page) shows that there may have been a slight shift towards higher percentages of older children over the last five years. (Where percentages are so small that they may put confidentiality at risk, they have simple been listed as <5%). Figure 1 (DfE 2014, no page) shows that most children stay for between one and six months with a slight reduction in longer stays over the last five years.

Table 2: Ages of Children in LASCHs 2010-14

Age at 31 March	% in 2010	% in 2011	% in 2012	% in 2013	% in 2014
Under 12	<5	0	<5	<5	<5
12	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5
13	12	10	9	6	7
14	27	20	26	23	14
15	34	32	30	33	36
16	17	29	26	27	26
17	6	<5	5	9	13
18+	0	0	<5	0	<5

Figure 1: Length of Stay in LASCHs 2010-14

The Department for Education (DfE) (2014, p.4) figures state that on 31 March 2014, 229 YPs were accommodated in these units:

- 45% of these were placed by Local Authorities on welfare grounds, nearly a 50% increase on the 2010 figure,
- 41% were female; the highest proportion in five years.

Figure 2: Number of Places and Children in LASCHs 2010-14

Figure 2 (DoE, 2014, p.2) shows how, while the number of children accommodated has fluctuated over the last five years, alongside numbers of

places available (and number of places held for young offenders), it is on a downward trend.

2.1.2 Educational Context

The majority of the pupils in this setting have had 'negative experiences of school' (NFER, 2011, p.4) and/or have been 'excluded from school before school leaving age' (Bhatti, 2010, p.33). Research shows a minority of permanently excluded pupils enjoy science (Daniels et al, 2003, pp. 21-22) and that 27% of PRU pupils believe that they were worse at science than their peers when in mainstream education (Solomon and Rogers, 2001, p.340).

As 'too often, children and young people who receive only a part-time education, or who have none at all, can become invisible to the local authority' (Ofsted, 2013, p.4), it is no surprise that when some of them enter LASCHs, there is no baseline information of their learning needs/abilities. However, it is often evident that they have very low levels of literacy and numeracy, which can make accessing science challenging.

My initial conversations with the pupils tend to confirm their strong dislike for the subject and a lack of understanding as to why it is relevant to them. Science lessons tend to be the first lessons they were removed from in mainstream education, possibly due to the risks of carrying out practicals and an associated lower tolerance for disruptive behaviour. Within science lessons, practicals are preferred over theory work as the writing is limited. This 'dislike of formal writing' is consistent with Daniels *et al* (2003, p.21) research with excluded pupils. However, practical work 'as practised' may add little to a pupil's learning (Osborne and Hodson, cited by Millar and Abrahams, 2009, p.59) and can provide a 'focus on the 'hands on' aspect of the task at the expense of the 'minds on' aspects' (Millar and Abrahams, 2009, p.63). Many YPs can have an almost "Pavlovian" resentment of science, which plays out in behaviour that limits teaching and learning.

Consideration needs to be given to the risks associated with a practical based on the individual YP (for example using Bunsen burners with a pupil convicted of arson, or using a scalpel with someone who self harms).

2.1.3 Class Size and Dynamics

Class sizes are typically small with a key performance indicator (KPI) of (see appendix 2):

Staff numbers on shift comply at all times with minimum standard required by Ofsted Care 1:3 Teachers 1:4

The purpose of this is to help manage behaviour and reduce the number of incidents leading to better learning opportunities and outcomes for the YPs.

In addition, YPs tend to be selected from the same friendship group rather than on the basis of age or ability, which can also minimise disruptive behaviour.

The disadvantages of this are the level of differentiation that may be required; you may have a GCSE pupil alongside a pupil who is unable to read or write or have such a friendly group that trying to teach is impossible as the lesson is more of a social opportunity than one that aids learning.

Variability in the length of stay of different YPs causes a constant changing dynamic as the individuals vie for their position within the social structure of the group. Stephenson (2007, p.129) recognises that developing 'stable learning groups' is difficult 'due to population churn resulting from large number of short sentences'. As learning is 'an evolving, continuously renewed set of relations' (Lave and Wenger, 2008, p.50) the frequent changes to an education group means it rarely settles long enough to allow full participation by all four YPs.

If Lave and Wenger's view is to be believed and learning is a social event that happens within a community of practice then it is vitally important to get the education groups right. All YPs will go through the same process; 'from entrance as a new comer, through becoming an old-timer with respect to new newcomers, to a point where those newcomers themselves become old-timers' (ibid, 2008, p.56).

When a new YP joins an education group they learn at the periphery (legitimate peripheral participation) while their confidence in an unfamiliar place builds.

As time passes, they become old-timers who understand how the unit operates, they (usually) engage more and our ultimate aim is full participation. My observation is that this process also happens in reverse: As the YP nears their release date, participation (engagement) declines and becomes towards the periphery again, albeit for a different reason.

2.2 Historic, Political and Socio-economic Context

2.2.1 A Brief History of the Secure Environment for Children

Although prison ships, and then Parkhurst Prison, in the early 19th century provided separate penal facilities for children, it was not until the Reformatory School Act (1854) that reformatories were established with the intention of 'saving troubled children from a fallen life' (Bateman and Hazel, 2014, p.2). They housed vulnerable children as well as young offenders as they do today. In 1908, the Children Act established a separate juvenile court which also dealt with crime and welfare issues together (Bateman and Hazel, 2014; The Justice Studio, 2014).

There have subsequently been many changes in thresholds (especially the age of criminal responsibility, which has stayed at 10 since the 1960s) and legislative powers over the years (Bateman and Hazel, 2014). In 1981 it was recommended that children should only enter secure accommodation via the legal route.

2.2.2 The Politics of 'Problem' Children

In 1993 the murder of two-year old James Bulger by two ten year old boys, and the media and public response, was probably a key turning point in youth justice policy (Bateman and Hazel, 2014). That same year the pendulum swung towards a more punitive youth justice system, as the Criminal Justice Act allowed for 'tougher sentences, taking into account offender history' (Bateman and Hazel, 2014, p.3). The following year the Criminal Justice and Public Order Act allowed Youth courts to use new custodial sentences for 12-14 year old persistent offenders. The harder tone of political rhetoric was accompanied by a call for more efficient and effective youth justice system. In 1999 Anti-social behaviour orders were introduced as an additional preventative measure, and disproportionately used on children (Bateman and Hazel, 2014).

Moving into the 21st century, the pendulum had started to swing back. It was still recognised that youth crime had to be punished, but children's rights came to the fore. 2002 saw the introduction of a presumption of early release and a judicial ruling that children in custodial institutions were entitled to the same services as those in the community. By 2008 there was a presumption that alternatives like intensive supervision and intensive fostering would be considered ahead of custodial sentences (Bateman and Hazel, 2014).

Deputy Prime Minister, Nick Clegg (2014) said in his speech:

'Criminals can't go unpunished, but young people who've made mistakes and committed crime can't simply be left on the scrapheap. The Coalition has reduced the number of young people in custody. But reoffending is sky high in this country and the answer lies in education and opportunity to change.'

In summary, while a custodial sentence in a LASCH is punishment, children are not sent there to be punished. Education is becoming increasingly important (and expected), within a wider context of rehabilitation and putting young people on the right track (MoJ, 2014 pp. 3-10). However, fewer children are being sent to LASCHs, and those that are, tend to be more persistent offenders for whom non-custodial alternatives have been deemed inappropriate. Consequently, there can be significant behavioural challenges that hinder education.

The aim of LASCHs may be to get YPs to 'contribute positively to society in adult life' (MoJ, 2014, p.3), but given their age the first test is often whether they can re-integrate into mainstream education. Given their frequently visceral response to science, this can be a significant challenge. This is why a more constructive experience of the subject while detained is important, otherwise the 'good work in custody can be quickly undone if a young offender returns to bad old habits' (MoJ, 2014, p.11).

2.2.3 Economic Context

The growing emphasis on efficiency since the late 1990s and the period of austerity and public spending cuts following the recession starting in 2007, have had a number of effects on LASCHs.

The introduction of privately run STCs in 2002 has meant that the number of LASCHs has been steadily declining, as the MoJ sees them as broadly interchangeable with STCs. The fact that the youth custodial population has fallen by 56% since 2003/04 (MoJ, 2014, p.8) has provided further reason to rationalise and consolidate institutions.

Financial pressures have driven Local Authorities (LA) to question whether LASCHs are good value for money, and to look to cheaper alternative private providers (MoJ 2014; Justice Studio 2014).

A place in a secure children's home is the most expensive of the three types of secure centres (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2013; Prison Reform Trust, 2014).

Table 3: Cost of Secure Estate for Young Offenders

Type	Cost 2012-13
Secure Childrens' Home	209,000
Secure Training Centre	187,000
Youth Offenders' Institution	60,000

In addition, the same financial pressures have driven down the purchase of welfare beds by LAs (Mooney et al, 2012) shifting the culture of, and nature of the challenge in LASCHs.

Since starting this project, two of the 17 LASCHs have closed. The changes on the horizon with the introduction of STC will increase the threat of further closures and therefore lead to increased competition within the sector (with institutions trying to demonstrate better value than each other). This and the current culture of not sharing information is counterproductive at a time when sharing best

practice could improve overall cost-effectiveness and increase competitiveness against other providers and potential new entrants into the market.

While this is a small scale project, it can make a small contribution to the goal of improving the cost-effectiveness of LASCHs. Indeed at least three of the recommendations in the Achieving Outcomes and Value for Money in Secure Children's Homes (2014) are relevant to this project:

'Recommendation to SCH: *Take steps to improve sourcing procedures and efficiency to bring costs in line with, or improve on, costs where possible.*'(ibid, p.57)

'Recommendation to SCH: *Move towards a culture of collective information sharing. The shared information should provide the foundations for a set of cost benchmarks those SCHs spending at above average levels can use as targets for future efficiency savings. Following this, all SCHs should aim to target improvements on their benchmarks over time with increased efficiency and cost control.*'(ibid, p.57)

'Recommendation to government: *SCHs should be recognised as a national resource requiring central coordination. A national strategy on the future of SCHs should be devised in order to improve the collecting and sharing of information, and assess ways to centralise resources in order to provide economies scale. This would ensure even greater value for money.*'(ibid, p.61)

2.3 Research Context

All LASCH in England and Wales were invited to be part of this research. YOIs were not included as the offenders are older and their educational provision is considered the 'poorest, with young people receiving an average of only 12 hours education each week' (MoJ, 2014, p.9). STCs were not included in the research because they are going through a restructuring and it is the Government's intention 'to withdraw from costly STC provision once replacement Secure College capacity is available' (MoJ, 2014, p.10).

The MoJ jurisdiction is mainly in England and Wales and as many powers have already been devolved to the Scottish Parliament the LASCH in Scotland was not included.

2.4 Autobiographical

In this public version, the autobiographical section has been adapted to reduce personal detail while retaining the context of my professional journey.

My professional and academic background has reinforced my belief in the power of education to transform futures. I left school with five O'levels, though not in the areas I had hoped to pursue. Determined to continue, I returned to college to study science subjects and later combined employment with day-release study to successfully complete a degree. This experience confirmed my conviction that persistence in education can open new pathways.

Over two decades of work across higher education, the environment, and industry provided me with skills in planning and strategy before retraining as a teacher in my early 40s. I began in mainstream schools, then moved into secure settings, where I discovered a particular strength in working with young people who had faced disrupted education and complex barriers to learning. Since 2011 I have taught science in a Local Authority Secure Children's Home, a role which, at the time of writing, had deepened my commitment to ensuring education plays a central role in rehabilitation and resettlement.

(Since then, my professional journey has continued through further leadership and specialist roles, but this dissertation reflects my practice and insights as they stood in 2014.)

3.0 Literature Review

This section critically assesses the literature and research linked to education in the secure setting with a more in-depth analysis of the issues around delivering effective and safe science lessons. However, as the 'literature on the education of prisoners is limited, and most of it relates to the education of adults' (Stephenson, 2007, p.137) I have extrapolated from other areas, as well as drawing on my own experience of LASCHs. For instance, research within PRUs has found that motivational and coping strategies are more important than curriculum strategies in addressing disaffection (Solomon, 2001).

The literature review is in two sections; education in the secure environment and teaching science to the YPs in this setting. In order to understand how key challenges (discussed in Section 1.1) can be overcome to teach science it is

essential to understand the purpose of education within LASCHs as well as the desired outcomes for the YPs in the secure setting. This includes understanding the impacts of literacy on science, the safe use of practicals and good practice in re-engaging disaffected youth.

3.1 Education in LASCHs

This section will look at the purpose and value of education in this environment. It then examines the areas that affect the teaching of all subjects in LASCH and are therefore not specific to science.

Value can refer to how relevant the YPs find education; as many as '63% of young men and 56% of young females aged between 15-17 year old in a YOI felt education would help them on release' (Murray, 2012, p.60). My experience is that while a YP is detained, they are understandably unsettled; they have been removed from their home, often awaiting sentencing and unsure about their future. Hayden (2008, p.31) found that coming to a LASCH 'leads to more disruption and trauma' so it is not surprising that education is not their main priority and they often do not see the relevance or importance of it. Maybe the difference in how YPs in YOI value education compared to those in a LASCH can be explained by their age and how many times they have been detained.

Value can also refer to the importance the institution gives education; in STCs education is 'set at such a high priority that no visits are allowed to interrupt lessons' (Stephenson, 2007, p.132). This is not my experience as YPs are often removed and brought back into lessons for meetings with professionals (medical, YOT, solicitor etc).

Stephenson asks (2007, p.134) 'what is the purpose of education in a LASCH or any custodial institution?' He suggests the following as the four main reasons (ibid p.134):

1. Reconnection to education training or employment,
2. Acquiring basic skills,
3. Vocational training,
4. Changing behaviour.

If vocational training and reconnection to education, training or employment are brought together Stephenson's theory could be represented by the Venn diagram below:

Figure 3: A Venn Diagram Showing the Purpose of Education in SCHs

Stephenson (2007) recognises that all the main reasons for education in this setting 'are closely allied' and 'all are necessary' (ibid, p.134) to stop reoffending. Seeing it as a Venn diagram makes this clear: If the SCH equips a YP with basic skills adequate enough to reconnect them with education or employment (position 3) but they do not change their behaviour then they will reoffend and return to a secure unit. If their behaviour changes and they acquire the basic skills of literacy and numeracy but are unable to get employment or have a school available to them on release (position 1) this could lead to them becoming disengaged again and wondering why they bothered and increase the likelihood of reoffending. If they change their behaviour and have employment or school to go to on release but they do not have the basic skills to remain engaged in education, training or employment again the likelihood of reoffended will increase.

It is vital, therefore, that education in a LASCH or any secure setting addresses all three simultaneously and aims for position 4 on the Venn diagram.

If, as 'research evidence suggests that engagement in education and training is one of the most important factors in reducing offending and reoffending' (YJB, 2006, no page), then any intervention has to be a 'learner-centred individualised programme[s] to motivate young people to gain basic skills' (ibid, no page). The key to this lies in good relationships between educators and YPs which take time to develop. Once the trust of the YPs has been gained it is easier to encourage them to work as they no longer see teachers as 'more of the same' (Mount, 1997, p.37). However, the following questions still need to be addressed:

- 'Can reconnection with education and training be readily achieved after disconnection through removal to a custodial sentence?' (Stephenson, 2007, p.136),
- 'Can new behaviours be readily acquired in a tightly controlled environment and then subsequently applied in a far less controlled one?' (ibid, p.136),
- Does it [education] mitigate the educational risk factors that young people bring with them on entry into such institutions? (ibid, p.128),
- Does it [education] have no discernible impact or could it even in some ways be involved in increasing the risk factors for reoffending?' (ibid, p.136).

If the above are to be successfully addressed during a YPs' detention then it needs to be recognised that they previously had a disrupted education and could have undiagnosed learning difficulties (see section 3.1.6) and that during their short sentence (107 days MoJ, 2013), proper and relevant assessment is essential.

3.1.1 Budget

As can be seen in Table 3, LASCHs have higher levels of funding than STCs or YOIs and 'there is a significantly higher ratio of teaching staff that tend to be qualified' (Stephenson, 2007, p.132). This could be explained by the fact that the YPs tend to be younger and LASCHs have welfare origins. Ascertaining a more detailed breakdown on budget was not possible; for example, the price of welfare

beds versus YJB beds or the percentage of income that went on education. This is probably because, as one report stated financial details were not included 'for reasons of commercial confidentiality' (Mooney et al, 2012).

3.1.2 Curriculum

To help overcome the barriers to engagement in education, staff in custodial establishments have suggested 'the range of programmes available for young people with special needs or poor literacy and numeracy skills' (YJB, 2006, no page) should be increased and there should be 'greater flexibility in the National Curriculum' (ibid, no page). This is in line with the new SEND Code of Practice (2105) that states 'all pupils should have access to a broad and balanced curriculum' (ibid, p.94) and Mount's (1997) view that if PRUs 'offered the same educational 'menu' as the mainstreams' (ibid, p.40) then the outcome would be same.

A diverse curriculum might not be practical in LASCH particularly where they have a small number of beds and consequently a smaller budget and therefore 'the curriculum is necessarily much more restricted due to lack of facilities than would be a secondary school or FE college' (Stephenson, 2007, p.132).

Mount (1997) went further in his conclusion on science teaching in PRUs by asking if there is 'a real, sensible and achievable entitlement curriculum for all?' (ibid, p.40). His research was in 1997 and today alternative qualifications to GCSEs are available, but again the key to this is keeping staff trained and up-to-date with alternatives. See section 3.1.8.

3.1.3 Assessment

According to Stephenson (2007) when a YP enters the secure setting there is an emphasis on educational assessment probably because the YPs arrives with 'limited' (ibid, p.137) or no previous data, however 'no standard approach is used which renders comparative analysis difficult' (ibid, p.132). The introduction of the electronic database known as eAsset in 2000 was to 'enable sharing of information about the YP between organisations' (YJB, 2014, no page) as it stores the following information about a YP:

- Case Notes,
- Incident Reporting,
- E-Learning,
- Multiple Sentences,
- eAsset Service Desk.

However, as it was Stephenson's view that (2007, p.138) 'as a predictive instrument, it is of somewhat limited educational use'. I met with the Quality Assurance and Development Manager to understand its limitations. The education department do not have access to this database and it only records data on literacy and numeracy, which can be entered in two different places in different formats. Further, it was stated that it was cumbersome to use and more significantly not compatible with systems used by the YOT or mainstream schools including PRUs (Bebbington, 2015).

'Most young people receive a literacy and numeracy assessment' (Stephenson, 2007, p.138), probably because this is what is recorded on the system. The Quality Assurance and Development Manager was not aware of recording of levels in other subjects, even those that are core.

It was recognised how frustrated the YPs become because '*they have done all this before*' yet Stephenson said (2007, p.139) it would

'not be unusual for young people with complex educational needs to complete the custodial phase of a DTO without anything resembling a complete educational assessment to occur, let alone services provided to meet these needs'.

The SEND code of practice (2015, p.95) states 'schools should assess each pupil's current skills and levels of attainment on entry, building on information from previous settings and key stages where appropriate'. There is a missed opportunity here to ensure a full educational assessment is done during a YPs detention.

In 2015 the eAsset system is due to be replaced with AssetPlus (YJB, 2014, p.3). The document AssetPlus Rationale (YJB, 2014, pp.3-13) discusses the changes that will be implemented learning from previous systems.

However, educational assessment (attainment and learning needs) is not included in this. Assessment in YJB terms is about behaviour and risk factors relating to offending but as can be seen below (Section 3.1.5) many young offenders have low prior attainment which could be down to having a special educational need. It feels as though the opportunity to put 'education at the heart of youth detention' (MoJ, 2013, p.5) is being missed: There is a disconnect between high level strategic decisions and what would be more appropriate/useful at the operational end.

If engagement in education is key to reducing re-offending and it is recognised that young offenders have undiagnosed learning difficulties then a vital opportunity is being missed to identify and understand a YPs educational needs. I am aware that decisions have been made not to assess a YP as they are only going to be with us for a couple of weeks.

3.1.4 Qualifications

The 'approach to education by prison management that is all about meeting key performance indicators' (Stephenson, 2007, p.137) is in contradiction to the desire to re-engage them. There is a definite pressure to gain qualifications for the YPs probably because LASCHs report regularly on the number of qualifications by YPs irrespective of their age; year 9 pupils have been entered for GCSE exams on more than one occasion. Is this appropriate? They would not be sitting exams if they were in school and this is counter intuitive to re-engaging them in education and training. Many have not been in school (see 3.1.5 below) and are now attending every day because they are detained and then have the immediate pressure of exams/tests.

I understand the desire to get young offenders re-engaged in education to reduce the risk of re-offending but as their sentences are short and their attainment levels below expected 'can significant qualifications be gained in just a matter of weeks?' (Stephenson, 2007, p.136). Furthermore, if they are pressured into sitting GCSEs before they are ready or old enough and they fail is disaffection being inadvertently encouraged?

Before I became a teacher I worked in business planning for many years and common sayings amongst colleagues were “be careful what you measure because it will drive behaviour” and “are we hitting the target but missing the point?” When I witness this drive to get qualifications for YPs I think the point has been missed, re-engaging is not about qualifications it is about enjoyment and getting the YPs to want to engage in education or training. As said by Ofsted (2013b, p.6) ‘Getting the grade is not the same as ‘getting’ the science’.

3.1.5 Special Educational Needs

During this research new statutory guidance has been issued by the Department of Education and the Department of Health titled SEND Code of Practice: 0-25 years (Jan 2015). It is the transfer of a statement of SEN to education, health and care (EHC) plans to ensure an holistic approach to planning between education, health and social care. The additional requirements arise from the Children and Families Act 2014 and cover disabilities, the Equality Act 2010 and the Mental Capacity Act 2005. It covers the age range 0 - 25, allows the individual and their parents/carers to be involved in decision making, and focuses on outcomes to help the individual to succeed in education and the transition into adulthood. More significantly for this setting it provides guidance on identifying and supporting YPs with SEN and includes specific guidance for those in youth custody (ibid, p14).

The Special Educational Needs and Disability (Detained Persons) Regulations 2015 details the new duties of maintaining and reviewing an EHC plan and arranging appropriate health and special educational provision for a detained YP.

A young person is said to have a learning difficulty if they have ‘a significantly greater difficulty in learning than the majority of others of the same age’ (ibid, p.16). However, ‘Slow progress and low attainment do not necessarily mean that a child has SEN’ (ibid, p.96). Certainly, low attainment in this setting could be explained by poor attendance at school and not a learning difficulty. Murray (2012, pp.27–30) found the following figures on attendance for the 15 -17 year olds in YOIs:

- 72% of young men and 84 % of young women said they had truanted,
- 88% of young men and 74% of young women had been excluded from school at some point,
- 36% of young men and 41% of young women were aged under 14 when they last attended school.

However, this needs to be balanced against the MoJ (2013, p.10) figures about detained YPs that state:

- 18% have an SEN compared to 3% in the general population,
- 23-32% have a generalised learning disability compared to 2-4% in the general population,
- 50% of 15-17 year olds in YOIs have the literacy levels of pupils aged between to 7-11.

Stephenson (2007) recognises that the actual level of SEN in the custodial population is speculative but thinks 'it is not unreasonable to assume this may be about one-half' (ibid, p.138).

As SEN data on the YPs is rarely available when they arrive into custody (Stephenson, 2007, pp.138-9) and there is an identified 'lack of support and specialist help' (YJB, 2006, no page) for them during their detention it is unacceptable that YPs leave custody 'without anything resembling a complete educational assessment let alone services provided to meet these needs' (Stephenson, 2007, p.138).

Steer (2005, p.55) highlighted that exclusions were four times more likely for pupils with SEN than those without and identified a close link with poor behaviour and the failure to identify SEN properly. The group found that schools with high standards of behaviour also have good SEN strategies.

Bringing all this data together it is clear that is a complex area; low attainment could be down to poor attendance (whether it is because of truancy or exclusions) and/or SEN. It is therefore essential that while a YP is detained any learning difficulty is diagnosed and addressed and an EHC plan developed prior to them leaving to ensure position 4 on the Venn Diagram above is achieved.

3.1.6 Emotional Social Behavioural Disorders (ESBD)

The SEND code of Practice (2015, p.96) says that ‘Persistent disruptive or withdrawn behaviours do not necessarily mean that a child or young person has SEN.’ It does go on to say however that such behaviour needs to be investigated further as there might be an underlying learning and communication difficulty, mental health issue or other cause. It recognises the importance of early intervention to prevent costly intervention at a later date. When a YP is detained, it is already at the costly intervention stage and the underlying cause has not been identified.

Mental health issues for detained people are estimated to be between 46 and 81% (ONS 2000) and young offenders have a higher incident of alcohol and drug use ‘than the general population’ (YJB 2004b). Department for Health (2013, p.7) found that problematic drinking is ‘far more common among offenders than the general population’ and that over 33% woman and over 66% men have an alcohol problem when entering prison. It also states that in the year before entering prison 69% have used at least one drug.

The YJB reported a ‘lack of willingness on the part of educationalists to tackle the causes of behavioural problems’ (YJB, 2006, no page) and Stephenson (2007, p.135) thought ‘that educators may be seen as separate from the disciplinary aspects of the regime’. Mount (1997, p.40) recognised that pupils taught in PRUs have very different and complex needs that need to be met before education is appropriate and that what is needed is ‘support, encouragement, constructive feedback and real resourcing’ (ibid, p.40). He goes on to say that PRUs cannot be a modified model of mainstream education as this will elicit the same response from the YPs.

If it is expected that teachers in LASCHs should be responsible for disciplinary aspects of behaviour, which can be caused by undiagnosed learning difficulties or mental health issues and addictions then surely appropriate training is key.

3.1.7 English as an Additional Language

I could not find any literature specific to English as an additional language (EAL) for YPs in custody; there is information on ethnicity, but not as a percentage of the total population. As figure 4 (NALDIC, 2014, no page) shows the occurrence of EAL has increased in both primary and secondary schools so it would not be unreasonable to speculate that there will also be an increase of EAL in custody.

Figure 4: Percentage of School Population with EAL

3.1.8 Training of Teachers

According to the YJB (2006, no page) educators (teachers, instructors and support staff) have 'identified their own lack of appropriate knowledge and skills as critical' and recognise that they need training 'in how to motivate disengaged young people'. The joint MoJ and YJB plan (2012, p.10) states that both LASCHs 'and STC have specially trained staff' and discusses the importance of developing their workforce (ibid, p.21). However, no specific training is required for teachers working in this environment, in fact instructors are not required to have a teaching qualification or expected to study for one once appointed. There is no expectation for educators to undergo additional training to work with young offenders. Given all the challenges that these YPs come with, it seems counter intuitive not to train all staff in identifying and managing these issues (drug abuse, mental health issues, SEN etc).

In addition to training to work with vulnerable YPs, educators need to keep abreast of changes in the curriculum especially if there is a focus on delivering a range of suitable qualifications tailored to the individual. Mount (1997, p.37), recognised that PRUs are educational establishments

'and like all schools, need to know what is expected of them in terms of the curriculum to be offered'. He 'believed that this lack of clear guidance was due to [his] own knowledge deficit and the isolation experienced by many teachers working in' pupil referral units'.

This isolation and knowledge deficit could also be true of teachers in LASCH, especially if teachers are not undergoing any professional development training, this may lead to the YPs not having access to the most appropriate qualifications and hinder re-engagement in education.

3.2 Teaching Science in LASCHs

Teaching in this environment is not an easy option; the YPs can have difficult and challenging behaviour and low academic attainment and teachers regularly experience failure and negative reactions. But as Mount (1997, p.37) found with pupils in PRUs it is 'where the work is; and the rewards'. Science lessons bring their own unique challenges; science requires good literacy skills for comprehension and good behaviour to carry out safe practicals. Other practical lessons within LASCH include the vocational subjects where safe behaviour but not literacy skills are required. English lessons can focus on literacy issues if necessary and while maths requires some literacy to progress it can focus on improving numeracy.

This section will focus on the issues relevant to delivering science lessons.

3.2.1 Safety in Science Lessons

The Health and Safety at Work Act 1974 put the onus on employers to ensure the health and safety of their employees and other people on their premises. This means the employer (the LA) has to make sure procedures and policies are in place to keep the teachers and pupils healthy and safe.

The Management of Health and Safety at Work Regulations 1999 state that hazards to the health and safety of teachers and pupils need to be identified and mitigated and documented via a risk assessment.

Safety in any practical subject has to come first. For science lessons in a LASCH it is essential that effective risk assessments (RA) are carried out for two reasons; one because of the equipment and chemicals used and two because of behavioural and learning difficulties of the YPs. If the philosophy of the SEND Code of Practice is to be followed then a 'broad and balanced curriculum' (ibid, 2015, p.94) should be available and barriers to learning removed.

There are many recognised learning needs and the specific needs of YPs in LASCH are often not met as are they have not been diagnosed. It may not be until they are having difficulty with practicals that attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) might be suspected or when they intentionally break equipment or ignore rules that oppositional defiant disorder (ODD) might be suspected. This puts the science teacher in a LASCH in a uniquely difficult position of having the responsibility to have an all inclusive scheme of work (SoW) but potentially and unwittingly putting themselves and others at risk.

It is not reasonable to expect a science teacher to be aware of all learning needs so collaboration with a special educational needs expert is essential.

3.2.2 Literacy in Science

In addressing the issues mentioned above when teaching science it would seem that practical lessons would be an appropriate way to overcome reliance on literacy but, as discussed in context section 2.1.2, practical work may limit progression in science.

A recommendation from Ofsted (2013, p.7) is to 'develop literacy through using science as a motivating context for pupils'. It recognised that having strong links between literacy and science increased achievement in both subjects (ibid, p.11). However, the report also linked the lower achievement of boys in science to their relatively weaker literacy skills because it limited reading and discussions about science as well as the writing up of science investigations (ibid, p.10).

The use of language in science is complicated; it is a 'combination and interaction of words, pictures, diagrams, images, animations, graphs, equations, tables and charts' (Lemke 1998; Jones 2000 cited by Wellington and Osbourne, 2001, p.6) with the expectation that pupils can effectively take notes, read text books, write reports and interpret data. Furthermore, familiar words have precise meaning in science (power, friction, resistance) and so many new words are introduced that it is akin to learning a new language. (Wellington and Osbourne, 2001, p.5)

Dirkx and Crawford (1993) studied teaching reading through teaching science to adult prisoners and found that 'making reading more contextually relevant and meaningful' (ibid, p.175) encouraged the adults to practice reading.

The challenge here is achieving engagement in science with YPs with poor literacy while using science to improve their literacy skills. However it is looked at, science requires a certain level of sophistication with language and as these YPs have had a disrupted education their 'difficulty with language causes difficulty with reasoning' (Byrne *et al* cited by Wellington and Osbourne, 2001, p.6).

3.2.3 Engagement in Science Lessons

Pupils who are critical of science lessons have often had 'negative experiences of school' (NFER, 2011, p.4). Research shows a minority of permanently excluded pupils enjoy science (Daniels *et al*, 2003, pp 21-22) and that 27% of PRU pupils believe that they were worse at science than their peers when in mainstream education (Solomon, 2001). My experience of teaching science in this setting supports this as the majority of YPs have a strong dislike of the subject.

The best science teachers set out to 'first maintain curiosity' in their pupils' (Ofsted, 2013b, p.4), However, in this setting it is about getting that curiosity back. The lessons need to be relevant, interesting and stimulating to capture and hold their attention, demonstrating how science can help them understand and inform their everyday actions (NFER, 2011), as pupils 'often fail to see the relevance of the work they are doing' (Ofsted, 2012). This is corroborated by Smith *et al* (2005, p.3) who found 'students appear to be more motivated by activities that they perceive as useful or relevant', however, this motivation may not go beyond the specific task'.

He recognises that to achieve motivation and engagement in science lessons is challenging due to the meta-cognitive and cognitive skills required to be successful (ibid, p.32).

My role as their science teacher is key as my 'approach, attitude and enthusiasm [will] influence their engagement' (Smith *et al*, 2005, p.4) and lessons that are fun and promote learning are 'more likely to cognitively engage' them (ibid, p.4).

3.2.4 Equipment

Stephenson (2007, p.132) found that teachers in LASCH tend to 'have access to a much wider range of facilities, including information and computing technology' while science laboratories 'tend to be inadequate'. Mount (1997, p.39) found that only 5.2% of PRUs considered the laboratory to be fully equipped and only 12.2% said they had a laboratory.

If there is not adequate equipment to carry out practicals then the only option is to teach theory lessons, possibly alienating YPs with low literacy levels. It will impact on their qualifications as some require a practical element, for example, AQA science GCSE consists of a coursework element worth 25% of the final mark.

If the purpose is to re-engage YPs in education and they have a fundamental dislike of science, re-integration into mainstream lessons will be more problematic if they have not learnt how to behave in science practical lessons.

4.0 Methodology and Method

This section explains my ontological, epistemological and methodological approach. It explores the pros and cons of each, the importance of triangulation along with ethical considerations.

The project objectives included understanding the differences between the LASCHs and the education departments to identify current practice in science teaching. The best way to do this was through a case study as it would provide 'an in-depth account of events, relationships, experiences or processes occurring' (Denscombe, 2003, p.32) in teaching science in secure units.

4.1 Ontological and Epistemological Assumptions

Working in a secure setting with 24 students means I am the only teacher for my subject and therefore I am the Head of Science, the teacher and the technician. I am only entitled to the standard 10% planning, preparation and assessment time (PPA) that a teacher in mainstream school gets. Any gained time after exams or during work experience does not exist in this setting as education is available for 50 weeks a year. This is balanced to some extent by less marking and no parent's evenings, but time is far too limited.

Ontology is about 'social reality' (Opie, 2010, p.18) and is described by Gray (2010, p.17) as 'the study of being, that is, the nature of existence'. The purpose of the questionnaire was to collect empirical data (gender mix, types of bed, budgets, etc) and therefore I am taking a determinist approach as I am collecting quantitative data 'in an attempt to lead to generalisability' (Opie, 2010, p.7). As a scientist I am naturally a positivist as my approach is to observe and measure 'in order to predict and control the forces that surround us' (O'Leary, 2007, p.5). That said as a scientist I am aware that proof of theories is only as good as the technology that is available to us at that point in time.

However, when carrying out the structured interviews I am a social constructivist: knowledge comes from understanding which in turn comes from interactions between people and therefore, culture and context are important. In this situation I am collecting accounts and perceptions through open ended questions from my peers to understand how our 'world is experienced and constructed' (Opie, 2010, p.20) as science teachers in the LASCHs are the only people who have this reality.

Epistemology is concerned with how you as an individual believe 'knowledge is acquired and how it can be communicated to others' (Opie, 2010, p.13). I feel that a person's epistemological stance has the biggest impact on how their research is constructed. Do you want quantifiable data from which generalizations can be made? That is the view of a positivist or an objectivist person. Or are you interested in gaining an insight to a situation through qualitative research? That is the view of an interpretivist or subjectivist person

(Opie, 2010, p.13). Ontology and epistemology are so closely linked and intertwined that it is not possible to understand who you are ontologically in isolation from what you believe epistemologically. For me, the key is in understanding your positionality to ensure your bias does not affect the findings of the research. As my case study is using different methods as required by the type of data I need for the outcomes, I am in this situation a 'blend of research procedures' (Opie, 2010, p.7). As long as I am aware of my positionality and the appropriateness of different methodologies/methods this is a strength; I will be aware of the advantages and disadvantages of each approach.

This research was based on my assumption that science teachers in other LASCH would be experiencing similar challenges, without support or guidance, and feeling isolated. For example, did they feel that the science national curriculum was suitable for pupils with such low levels of literacy and numeracy? Or like me did they believe for this group of young people it is about re-engaging them in education: Discussions with YPs as part of my previous research project (Chellew, 2013) showed their dislike of science was the starting point, in their opinion, of things going wrong. It is essential therefore to re-engage them in science if the long-term plan is to re-integrate them into education. (See sections 2.1.2 and 2.2.2)

As the research came from the aspiration to improve my own practice I wanted to share my experiences and learn from other more experienced teachers and identifying how teachers can support and learn from each other. I wanted to know if the gaps in my knowledge and the feeling of isolation were unique to me or something felt by other teachers in this setting. I was not sure if it was down to the fact that I am teaching outside my specialism as I trained to teach mathematics even though I have a science degree or if it was as a result of how these units operate. I wanted to ascertain if Mount's (1997) findings of isolation experienced by teachers in PRUs were true for teachers in LASCHs. Was it my lack of experience as a secondary science teacher or the fact that I was working in isolation that led to feelings of insufficiency? Was it just me? Or were science teachers in other units having similar experiences? My intuition and discussions with other teachers in the unit led me to believe it was about how LASCHs operated and that I had an opportunity to improve things for myself and my peers.

Mount (1997) wanted to understand from his research into science teaching in PRUs how teachers were overcoming the challenges of teaching in that setting.

4.2 Case Study as a Methodology

In the lead up to this research project, discussions with my HoE highlighted that each LASCH operated differently and delivered different subjects and that no one had a clear overview of how they all operated. In order to improve the delivery of science it was also necessary to understand the difference between LASCHs. Using a case study as the methodology would give 'an insight into the context of a problem as well as illustrating the main point' (Fry, Ketteridge and Marshall, cited by Wilson, 2013, p.257). It also means that a 'variety of research methods' (Denscombe, 2003, p.38) would be available allowing the flexibility to change the approach, if needed, as the project progressed (Gray, 2010, pp.169-70). As this was the first time a project of this type had been attempted and it was unclear what the findings might be, it was important that the research was not limited by the methodological approach.

Case studies are not a panacea and have been criticised for their validity in terms of limitations and construct (Wilson, 2009, p.205) and the bias introduced by the researcher (O'Leary, 2007, p.116). In this research project the point that 'theory, reliability, and validity are at issue' (Flyvbjerg, 2006, p.221) would be negated if all units and teachers were part of the project (complete collection sampling) as I would have the full picture and not just the views of those that have self-selected as a result of volunteering.

To overcome any bias I might bring to this research, it was intended that the findings would be presented back to the all participants to give them the opportunity to clarify and/or resolve any outcomes they were not confident in, as suggest by Yin (cited by Wilson, 2009, p.205). This would have had the added benefit of encouraging collaboration as it would have been the first time the participants had got together. This meeting would have help alleviate the issues of validity due to my actions not being impartial as I have a vested interested in the project being a success. Unfortunately, the regular meetings of HoE were delayed, meaning feedback was not possible within the timescale of this project.

Criticisms of case studies could come from a different understanding of the term “case study” and whether it is used as a methodology or method. As a scientist my understanding of the term case study is that you are trying ‘to catch the complexity of a single case’ (Stake, 1995, p.xi), such as an individual patient, (a method). In this research, as a social scientist, my understanding of a case study is that there is ‘a need for a general understanding’ (Stake, 1995, p.30) so the meaning of a case study is different: The case is unique due to the context but information is being gathered from many individuals to gain a general understanding of the LASCH and the delivery of science.

I think it is important to keep in mind the purpose of the research, and not get too embroiled in the advantages and disadvantages of methodologies and methods: ‘Good social science is problem driven and not methodology driven’ (Flvbjerg, 2006, p.242) and the findings might not be ‘generalizable’ (O’leary, 2007, p.116) as the data collected may be contradictory or too small a sample. However, research should not be shied away from due to the limitations of different methodologies or methods in fact research ‘is quite simply a central element in learning and in the achievement of new insight’ (Flvbjerg, 2006, p.237)

Using a case study as a methodology provided a sound approach for holistically exploring an in depth understanding of educational delivery in this specific and real context, with the focus being on the processes and relationships that lead to identifying and sharing best practice; the desired outcomes (Denscombe, 2003, pp.30-31).

As there are not many secure units (17 at the outset and 15 by the end) it was a small enough number for every unit to be invited to be involved in the research. A large amount of data was collected from 12 HoE and 7 science teachers, so it was important not to select quotes and/or data to ‘illustrate specific points’ (Swan, 2006, p.35) that supported my own views, known as the ‘Bartlett effect’ (ibid, p.35). I needed to remain aware of biases and subjectivities as the mere act of selecting these ‘critical events’ would portray ‘positionality’ (ibid, p.18) in the project and may accidentally exclude significant findings.

Being aware of bias, subjectivity and the use of a critical friend went some way to overcome the criticisms of case studies but this methodology also allowed 'the validation of data through triangulation' (Denscombe, 2003, p38). Triangulation is a 'powerful way of demonstrating concurrent validity, particularly in qualitative research' (Cohen, 2011, p.195 cited Campbell and Fiske 1959) which lacks the repeatability sought through more quantitative studies. Given that 12 returns were received from HoE and 7 from the science teachers, it was not possible to have quantifiable, repeatable, statistically significant data.

4.3 Methods

This section looks at the general advantages and disadvantages of questionnaires and structured interviews and the specific problems I encountered.

4.3.1 Questionnaires

A questionnaire was an appropriate way of collecting data in order to establish 'a broad impression' (Clough and Nutbrown, 2012, p.159) of the differences between units 'with little or no personal interaction' (ibid, p.159). This was important as the physical locations of the units meant it would not be possible to visit them all. It was piloted with my line manager, and refinements made (Cohen, 2011, p.377) to ensure it used simple unambiguous language (Bell, 2003, p.121) (refer to Appendix 3). The project and the questionnaire were discussed at the secure accommodation network education (SANed) meeting in May 2014. Feedback from this meeting was very positive with all HoE present supporting the project. The draw back here was that as a project like this had not happened before they wanted to use this opportunity to collect data of interest to them, but not necessarily relevant to my research. I decided to collect the data requested by them as it would increase participation in the project. As questionnaires are used as 'research tools through which people are asked to respond to the same set of questions in a predetermined order' (Gray, 2009, p.338) it was a quick and easy way of collecting mainly factual data (gender mix, types of bed, budgets, etc) 'without the presence of the researcher' (Cohen, 2011, p.377). However, the disadvantages to this approach meant;

- I missed opportunity to develop relationships with the HoE, enabling me to read body language and build rapport to encourage participation. However, as the response rate was 80% this was not really an issue and confirmed that my decision to let them have ownership of the questionnaire to be a good one,
- I could not guarantee they were not offended (harmed) (Cohen, 2011, p.377) by any of the questions,
- I could not be fully confident they had informed consent.

4.3.2 Structured Interviews

Ideally, I would have interviewed every science teacher within the secure setting face to face, but this was not practical given their locations across England and Wales, potential costs and the time available. Group interviews may have been quicker but logistically it was difficult to organise as the units did not stick to local authority term dates and followed their own calendar. Added to this was the uncertainty of reliability of the results as people may not feel secure enough to be honest in group setting compared to an individual interview (Denscombe, 2003, pp.166-8). I wanted to ensure that everyone was given the same opportunity to express their views and give myself the opportunity to explore and clarify more complex ideas, if they arose. The best way of doing this was via a structured interview as it is a questionnaire with a set of pre-determined questions (Denscombe, 2003, pp.166-8) discussed over the phone. The questions for the structured interview (see appendix 4) had a mixture of closed and more open-ended questions which allowed the probing of complex ideas.

In the development of the questions I considered the order and length of time it would take to conduct the interview. I tried to ensure it was not unnecessarily intrusive, offensive, made assumptions or seemed irrelevant (Denscombe, 2003, pp.153-5).

My intention was to contact individuals on the phone in advance to discuss the scope, aims and ethos of the project (Denscombe, 2003, p.159) to build rapport, trust, and help create a supportive and non-judgemental environment, required for honest and open responses (including disclosures of failures alongside successes, as both inform learning).

However, at the SANed meeting this was discussed and the HoE agreed that they would discuss this project with their science teacher and encourage participation (see ethics below). This affected my decision on whether to record the telephone interview or not as I was concerned that if they felt they had to be part of the project and then their responses were recorded they might not be as forthcoming. Therefore, I did not record the conversation.

For this to be successful I was continually aware of the complexities of people, including myself, and how this might impact on honesty and openness. I was asking questions that could make the respondent feel judged or embarrassed (O'Leary, 2004, p.162) so I volunteered experiences from my own teaching to make them feel more comfortable. I needed to be aware of risk of bias in this approach as, in an interview, teachers might say 'what they feel the researcher wishes to hear' (Cohen, 2011, p.175) possibly because they were 'too shy or embarrassed to reveal their true feelings' (ibid, p.175). Additionally, as the teaching is with vulnerable YPs exploring personal experiences and feeling could be painful for the participants. This highlights the importance of developing good working relationships and building rapport which is potentially harder over the phone than face to face.

4.4 Triangulation

Triangulation is 'working to substantiate an interpretation or clarify its different meanings' (Stake, 1995, p.173). Triangulation is imperative in this research as the case study 'describes a subculture that had rarely been the topic of previous study and discovers key phenomena' (Yin, 2009, p.7)

However, the uniqueness of this project and the limited literature meant that triangulation was carried out by extrapolating from other relevant literature as discussed in the literature review.

4.5 Ethical Considerations

Given that I work in LASCH the ethical considerations might be fraught with difficulties, but as the case study focused on teachers and not vulnerable YPs the ethics were easier to deal with. That does not mean there were no ethical issues to consider just that they were not as extensive as they would have been if I was involving vulnerable YPs.

I secured 'approval from relevant authorities' (Denscombe, 2003, p.172) by writing a letter outlining the aims of the research project (see appendix 5). A similar outline of the project was also sent to HoE to gain their informed consent (BERA 2011) (see appendix 6).

The teachers were issued letters outlining the project to gain their consent (see appendix 7) (BERA 2011). However, I was conscious that there was a strong possibility that they had been encouraged to participate in the project by their HoE and that they might feel coerced into talking to me which is against the philosophy of this research. I started the telephone interview by asking if they were aware of this project to assess if there had been a discussion with the HoE. If they were not aware, I outlined the scope of the project and asked if they would like to be resent a copy of the letters and time to read them prior to being involved. If they were happy to proceed or were aware of the research I explained the ethical issues (see below) and their right to withdraw and/or not answer specific questions and assured them of confidentiality. The majority of teachers were aware of the project and keen to be part of it and excited by the possible outcomes of more collaborative working.

While researching and writing up this dissertation I needed to be mindful of a number of ethical issues;

- With such a small group of people I needed to make sure I presented the findings in the data analysis section in such a way that their responses were not attributable to individuals unless they chose to be identified (BERA, 2011). If they felt I was not respecting their entitlement to confidentiality (BERA, 2011) or their right to anonymity (Denscombe, 2003, p.163) they would not have been honest and open,
- I needed to accept that others might not feel as passionate about my research project as me and even though I did not 'coerce' participation (Cohen, 2011, p.377) I was concerned the HoE may have,

- I needed to be clear with participants on the aims/limitations of, and their role in, my research (BERA, 2011), in case I could not implement a change especially as they were genuinely quite excited about the possible changes such a project could initiate,
- I needed to ensure my actions/questions did not cause the participants to withdraw (Denscombe, 2003, p.178), as is their right (BERA, 2011) by being be offensive or making assumptions or antagonising them (Bell, 2003, p.136),
- I used a critical friend to ensure the data was used appropriately, recognizing that small scale qualitative research is about exploration and description, not statistically valid conclusions (Denscombe, 2003, pp. 232-233).

5.0 Analysis of Findings

This section looks at the implications of the different units (size and type) and education departments on teaching science. The analysis of findings from the HoE can be found in appendix 8 and from the teachers in appendix 9.

It is important to understand the difference between the units and the education departments as this could potentially have an impact on the delivery of the science lessons and therefore the identification and sharing of best practice. For example, small units may not have the resources to deliver science practicals and therefore do not need to know how to deliver the best practical lesson. This is discussed in more detail below.

Unfortunately, during the research stage of this project two of the secure units closed and of the 15 remaining units only 10 had science teachers in post, two left during this research. Given the changes happening within the secure setting I was pleased to have 12 returns from the HoE and 7 from the teachers.

5.1 Implications of Unit Analysis

Not all the data collected in this section would have an impact of how education, including science would be run. The type, size and percentage occupation varied so much that it could not be analysed in any meaningful way to effect how SoW are planned and delivered. However, the length of stay and age on admission could help us with the planning and delivery of lessons and/or qualifications.

Most of the YPs are in KS4 and are with us between 3 and 7 months. This will be discussed in more detail below in conjunction with NC levels and progression.

5.2 Implications of Education Department Analysis

The extent to which the data gathered in this exercise helps in the planning and delivery of effective lessons is reflected in the depth of analysis carried out.

5.2.1 Allowances

The allowances paid to teachers varied and included secure unit, community homes, special educational needs and teaching and learning responsibility. There was no consistency and this could have an impact on morale if, teachers are getting paid less for doing the same job because they are employed by a different unit. I did contact the DfE to see if teachers within secure units should receive SEN allowance and their answer (see appendix 10) in an email (2015) says that the local authority is best placed to decide if the teachers receive an allowance for SEN, this is why there are localised pay conditions.

5.2.2 Term Dates

The units have different approaches to how terms are organised. This would not impact on identifying and sharing best practice other than it becomes logistically more difficult to organise meetings. Most units have a 6 week term and this timescale can be used for developing SoW.

5.2.3 Ofsted Reports

I did not receive any Ofsted reports from HoE even those who were prepared to share it. This could be because there is competition between units for beds and collaborative work rarely happens or simply because the HoE forgot. I did not want to keep asking for it and have my actions lead to a decision to withdraw from the research (Denscombe, 2003, p.178).

The Ofsted reports for LASCH did not appear to be publicly available; I checked on both the justice inspectorate and Ofsted websites. The only inspection reports available were for STCs, YOIs and adult prisons. I now know that the names of

the LASCHs do not appear on the Ofsted website and that you have to search using their unique reference number (URN). If more time had been available I would have requested the URN from the LASCHs in order to identify any good practice highlighted in the Ofsted reports that could be shared.

5.2.4 HoE Qualifications

All of the HoE that responded are qualified teachers, mainly secondary. This is, in my opinion, an excellent finding as they have an understanding of education. The advantage of a secondary trained HoE is that they will understand what is needed in terms of planning and delivering GCSE or equivalent exams. Anecdotal evidence from the instructors, who are supervised by managers without an educational background, is that they do not understand the time required to plan, prepare and assess work. The advantage of having primary trained HoE is that they will have a good understanding of the KS2 NC levels that the majority of YPs enter the system with. (See assessment below).

When you train as a secondary teacher you learn about NC level 4 and up and the lower levels are not covered. Both secondary and primary teachers in the secure setting need to be able to effectively teach from KS2 to KS4 so a mix of secondary and primary trained teachers would be ideal.

All HoE that responded did some teaching but this varied considerably. As long as HoE are doing some teaching it will remind them of the challenges their staff encounter every day when teaching young offenders.

5.2.5 Assessment

The majority of units assess maths and English on entry and exit with regular assessments to assess progress (monthly, termly or 3 monthly depending on the length of stay). Two units do not assess science at all. If re-offending rates within a year are as high as 71%, (MoJ, 2014, p.3) then the same YPs are coming back into the secure estate and are being pointlessly re-assessed using different methods. Thought needs to be given to how the barriers to education can be reduced and/or removed in order to re-engage YPs in education. This re-assessing must frustrate them.

It would be better if educational professionals could access a database with this information and have a discussion with the YPs about it. Many have already been let down and/or lost in the system and this will just confirm their negative opinion of “authority”. The huge range in the different types and timings of assessment on the YPs is in line with Stephenson’s findings (section 3.1.3).

That said assessment is showing that YPs do make excellent progress while detained. There is a general agreement that initial assessments show the YPs to have a NC level 3 for maths, English and science and that their final assessment shows an increase to NC level 4. One HoE commented that

‘up ½ a level is minimum.’

Given that their average length of stay is between 3 and 7 months this is excellent progress.

One HoE made an excellent observation about initial assessment

‘very variable – in line with what I see – is NC level 3 the mode?’

Certainly, from my experience this is true and it is the mode and not the mean. I have assessed year 10 YPs with NC level 1 in science, but have also had YPs with a level 6. In terms of planning and delivery of lessons this is useful data.

There is no evidence to suggest that primary and secondary trained HoE have a different approach to assessment.

5.2.6 Education Staff and Curriculum Provision

This was very difficult to analyse because of the differences between each unit (see appendix 8). In general qualified teachers taught maths, English and science. However, in one unit English was taught by a primary teacher but this unit did not teach maths, in another unit science was taught by an unqualified teacher. English, science and PE were taught in all units that responded.

To demonstrate some of the difficulties that arose here are some of the comments on the returns:

- *All staff are involved with vocational training,*
- *Science teacher also teaches child development and life skills,*
- *Maths teacher also teaches French and Food,*
- *SRE taught by trained care staff,*
- *'Citizenship - 1 afternoon per week. Includes a programme of drug and alcohol awareness',*
- *'Careers -1 visit of half a day every 2 weeks'.*

Full analysis was further hindered by some returns indicating that the subject was taught and not giving a full time equivalent (fte). Having gone through the data I understand the difficulties with giving a detailed and complete picture so I have grouped together the teachers (qualified and unqualified) with the instructors and kept support (TA and/or care) staff separate. This is not ideal some TA and care staff are responsible for delivering part of the curriculum but it gives a good overall picture of what subjects are taught and the extent to which support is available in the lesson.

As the graph shows not all national curriculum subjects are taught in every LASCH. This could be because units are too small to justify having a teacher to cover every subject and a pragmatic approach has to be taken as to what can be delivered. It must be remembered that this is a snapshot of what is happening at a particular point in time and differences could be partly explained by staff turnover.

Figure 5: NC Subjects Taught and Supported in LASCH

There is a good provision of vocational subjects with only one unit not providing any.

The amount of support in each lesson varied from care staff or '*support staff in each lesson*' to '*depending on need*'. This is also shown on the graph above.

One unit is fortunate enough to have an enrichment coordinator to organise '*enrichment weeks – our school holidays – and also look at bringing in external support and training to enrich the curriculum and support young people's individualised curriculum*'.

5.2.7 Class Size

This varied across the units. I would have expected this to be consistent as key performance indicator (KPI) A1 states (see appendix 1):

'Staff numbers on shift comply at all times with minimum standard required by Ofsted Care 1:3 Teachers 1:4'

If there are more than 4 YPs in a class then there is an additional member of staff in the form of a teaching assistant (TA) or care staff.

In terms of sharing best practice, this does have an impact. A lesson with consistent support will be organised and delivered differently to those that do not have support. Science practicals are safer to deliver if an additional member of staff is present as potential risks are mitigated by their presence. The number of YPs in the lesson will also have an impact on how the lesson is delivered.

5.2.8 Special Educational Needs

The graph shows the percentage of YPs with SEN, English as an additional language (EAL) and emotional social behavioural disorders (ESBD) from 10 units. 2 Units were unable to provide the data stating '*unknown as of yet not recorded fully sorry*'.

Figure 6: Graph Showing % YPs with Educational Needs in LASCH.

The level of identified SEN varied across the units and was between 5-36%. As there is a general acceptance that the YPs are NC level 3 and in KS4, would there be an expectation that there would be a higher percentage of SEN? As one HoE wrote on their return *'that we are aware of'* implying that they believe there might be more. These unknown SEN YPs are probably down to the fact that the YPs have been lost in the system and have not attended school for many months or possibly years prior to coming into the secure setting and therefore their full educational needs have not been assessed as Stephenson (2007) found (see section 3.1.3).

The level of ESB varied between 10-52% across the units. Given that the YPs are detained on criminal or welfare grounds, would more YPs with ESB statements be expected?

How can effective lessons be planned and delivered, let alone shared, if the special educational need of the YPs is not known? As effective assessment is not in place when they arrive this could potentially be an issue throughout their detention and when they leave and enter another educational setting.

The level of YPs with English as an additional language varied between 0-10% across the units.

5.2.9 Budget

5 units do have a separate budget for education which ranged from £8K - £34k. If I assume the returns that stated 'NA' and 'good question' mean they do not have a separate budget, then this means 4 units do not have a separate budget for education. The remaining units said:

- 'SLA still to be agreed',
- 'not released yet',
- 'not prepared to share this information'.

I was surprised to see that some HoE did not appear to have control over their budget. My concern here is how can you effectively plan if you do not have sight of or control over your budget?

I was hoping to ascertain if there was an increase in the education budget with an increase in the number of beds and if the type of bed affected the budget, but unfortunately the sample is too small to make any meaningful analysis.

5.2.10 Analysis of Science Teaching:

All of the 12 units that participated in the research teach science but only 5 of them have laboratory facilities. This will impact on the sharing of best practice as not all units have laboratories and therefore cannot deliver practical lessons.

The budgets, where the figures were available, were small and ranged from approximately £1-4000. However, responses also included:

- not assigned,
- have not got one,
- Not fixed,
- As required,
- No specific budget.

As with the education budget, how can you plan effectively if you do not know what your budget is? It would be useful to compare this budget to the budget for other practical subjects.

5.3 Analysis of data from Science Teachers

As you would expect from science teachers the degrees are quite varied and ranged from physics to zoology (refer to appendix 9). There are two teachers with a degree in PE and geography. One is a qualified primary school teacher and the rest secondary all have qualified teacher status (QTS). I am a qualified maths teacher. None of the units have a full time teacher dedicated to teaching science. If they are employed full time, they are involved with teaching other subjects (see appendix 9).

The time spent teaching in secure setting and outside the secure setting varied as shown by the graph below:

Figure 7: Number of Teaching Years in Mainstream and Secure Setting

5.3.1 Training for SEN/ESBD

Not many teachers had had training for SEN/ESBD. The training the teachers had undergone varied in quantity and quality, some had undergone training prior to coming into this setting, some was in-house and some external.

Only three teachers had undergone training for dyslexia and low levels of literacy and only two for low levels in numeracy and ESB. This included ASD and speech and language therapy which was found to '*quite useful*' as you should not '*assume they understand your vocabulary*'.

One unit had provided 'Human Givens' training for education staff to help them better understand and manage challenging behaviour, but this has since stopped which is a shame because the teacher described it as '*extremely useful*'. They now have a mental health nurse at the unit.

5.3.2 Overcoming SEN/ESBD

Staff have developed resources to overcome low levels in literacy and numeracy and challenging behaviour and these are summarised in appendix 9.

Comments from teachers included:

- '*I am happy with my knowledge to teach YPs with SEN/ESBD but it is self taught*',
- '*it is from previous experience in EBD schools*',
- '*it is nightmare as you need to differentiate by age and ability*',
- '*the level of differentiation means that you are often doing four lessons in one*',
- '*poor behaviour limits practicals but so does not having a proper environment.*'

The finding here is that staff have not been trained while working in the LASCH but have previous experience or training.

5.3.3 Lesson Support

Support in lessons varies. Some units have TAs in every lesson and may also have care staff to support as well. Some only have care staff and no TAs. If requested TAs and/or care staff are in lessons but in one unit this is only if they are available. This was in line with the findings from the HoE.

One unit is lucky enough to have a technician to sort out the practical lessons while the majority do not have any extra time to do this.

5.3.4 Internet Access

All teachers have internet access but use it with varying degrees of success to support their lessons. Those that can use videos from YouTube found it '*has been fabulous*'. Others find it frustrating as sites are not unblocked properly and the internet cannot be used for the lesson, making the delivery of planned lessons impossible.

The YPs have internet access at 7 of the units. Two of the unit appear to have an excellent IT package to block and monitor websites usage. Others are using it on a '*trust basis*' while some are visually monitoring to ensure inappropriate sites are not accessed. There is concern that some staff are not controlling this as well as others. Where units have got a good handle on this there is good use of games and online courses for the YPs to enhance their learning and increase the qualifications they can achieve.

5.3.5 Lesson Planning and Content

Teachers get their lesson ideas from a range of places:

- KS3 SoW,
- KS3 topics linked to AQA units,
- KS4 SoW from exam boards (ELC and GCSE),
- Bought in resources,
- Linked up with local schools as recommended by Ofsted,
- TES,
- CLEAPPs,
- apt awards,
- Internet,
- Imagination.

With the exceptions of apt awards, AQA units and linking with another school, this is what you would expect from a mainstream teacher.

What is absent here is collaborative working. The majority of teachers (with one exception) have said they are more than happy to share and get feedback on their lesson, so why does this not happen? I would suggest that part of the issue here is that lesson plans or risk assessments are not routinely used (see 5.3.7 below) so sharing a lesson plans creates more work which teachers are understandably reluctant to do. This may be supported by the fact that even though teachers promised to email me lesson plans for their best lesson none were forthcoming due to the extra work it would create.

The balance between the three sciences was not consistent; some units felt they had a balance; some were constrained by available equipment; biology dominated in 3 units and one favoured physics.

It is disappointing that collaborative working is not happening as every teacher mentioned lessons that were successful. If lesson plans were combined then a broad, balanced range of topics and approaches would be available. This may take teachers out of their comfort zone, but it will help improve their teaching.

The majority said they stick the NC for KS3 and KS4, but recognise that this is difficult given the length of sentences.

One teacher said that they *'try to have an even balance of chemistry, physics and biology but select for practicals and life relevance'*. The lack of a laboratory or any equipment means the simplest practical cannot be carried out and the NC cannot be met. Personally, I chose qualifications that meet the NC but it might cross different year groups.

As there is only one science teacher and no subject head for guidance they can chose what and how to teach. This is reflected in the following comments:

'No one to lean on, it is a bit scary'

'I have never been told what to teach - I look after myself'

Given the constraints of time, equipment, behaviour and low attainment, is the NC relevant?

5.3.6 Qualifications for YPs

There is quite a pressure to get qualifications for the YPs. This is best captured by '*GCSE is difficult with short sentences but that is the expectation.*' I think this comes from the fact that monthly reports include 'the number of qualifications by YP'. To me this is not a meaningful measure, given the age of the YPs, the length of their sentence or the fact that for GCSEs exam timetables are not within our control. It does not link into the KPIs.

I did not receive any data on qualifications achieved from any unit but I did get a data on the different qualifications and exam boards as shown in appendix 9. This included none, ELC, apt awards, Crest and GCSE. If the teachers want to work effectively to achieve the best possible outcomes for the YPs, then the number of qualifications needs to be streamlined. This would be advantageous to the YPs who are re-admitted, as they could continue with the course they have already started. I have also found that by encouraging KS4 YPs to complete their GCSE coursework that when they have left they have continued with the course.

5.3.7 Health and Safety

While there is evidence of good practice there is a lack of awareness around health and safety for science. Not all units have a policy and there is no clear ownership of it. Responsibility for writing it and updating it varies;

- science teacher,
- HoE,
- Never updated,
- Don't know.

Only 50% of the teachers had undergone any H&S training, one said the training was not useful at all and two had completed training prior to coming into the secure setting. Over 50% either stated they were not members of CLEAPPs or were unsure. One was a member at a county level.

Over 50% of the teachers do not have a risk assessment proforma and even if they do it does not mean that they are being carried out.

Statements from teachers on H&S included;

- just common sense,
- H&S and risk assessment will be part of in-service training (INSET),
- CLEAPPS training was very useful as it has lesson plans with risk assessments,
- As I do everything, prep etc, awareness of protocols are very useful,
- Created my own RA.

It is quite worrying that the understanding of H&S appears quite limited. Before best practice can be identified and shared, staff need to be trained properly.

Linked into this is how the YPs are introduced into science lessons. Again there is good practice that includes;

- observing the YP for a week or two before making a decision as to whether practical lessons are appropriate,
- 1:1 lessons in science,
- induction pack.

But as one teacher said '*the YPS are just thrown in, nothing formal*'. Certainly, I feel risks are taken when YPs are placed in practical subjects and I feel disconnected from the decision making process: A senior management meeting takes place once a week where the managers discuss the individual and changes to their risk assessment. This information is filed in two places and is quite time consuming to keep on top of it.

5.3.8 Equipment

Scientific equipment is bought from expected suppliers:

- Unilab
- Phillip Harris
- Tim Star
- SciChem
- Griffin

In general the teacher is responsible for ordering it but for one unit the Local Authority (LA) does it. The issues around ordering included;

- Not being able to buy small enough quantities,
- Would not know where to start,
- Time and sourcing it.

No one seemed to have a problem with finding a budget for the equipment if they could make a case for it.

Efficiency could be improved by having central purchasing and sharing the equipment. The inability to source and purchase equipment should not be a limiting factor to delivering effective science lessons.

5.3.9 Timetable

None of the units teach science full time. A teacher may be employed full time and have science as part of their timetable and teach other subjects. Part-time teachers of science tend to teach only science but this is not always the case.

The amount of PPA provided is different for each teacher as shown below:

- *As we provide cover internally, I am not guaranteed any PPA,*
- *PPA Thursday and Friday morning, but this varies, loads of PPA,*
- *5 PPA in 2 weeks,*
- *4 -8 PPAs per week (varies),*
- *At least 2 PPAs per week,*
- *One day a week (0.8 fte).*

On top of this are the weekly changes in timetabling and the issue that staff 'receive the timetable Sunday evening'. Certainly this is an issue for planning and for me not knowing the timetable until the weekend before makes it difficult to prepare for practicals, for example ordering hearts for dissection.

5.3.10 External Links

The importance of having external links was best explained as follows:

'As we work in a small environment you can become very insular and this makes it difficult to keep on top of changes. When you are stuck in small organisation you become stale as you have no one to discuss things with. It [external links] keeps me focused and positive, Standards are kept up as all in the group are outstanding. Otherwise it is always ticking away at the back of my mind that I have missed something. No links with other schools makes it incredibly hard to teach GCSE. 3 times a year there is a head of science conference, its free and cover is paid – very useful as it keeps you on the ball and on top of changes.'

It is good to see that everyone has an external link of some description as shown below.

Schools	Yes							
Universities	No	Yes						
PRU	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
LA	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No

Apart from the advantages mentioned above other positives that the teachers identified were:

- I can access a SENCO,
- For borrowing equipment,
- School link is really good,
- Invaluable, and
- Very useful for ideas and equipment.

This needs to be balanced against the slightly negative comments below:

- Mixed, some good some not so good,
- Too early to tell if useful but have lessons and SoW, and
- Pick up a few ideas but not that relevant.

Taking all this into account external links should be developed to keep teachers abreast of developments and changes and improve teaching standards.

6.0 Conclusions

This research project went some way to meet its objectives, but its potential lies in which changes are implemented as a result of the findings. It has identified some common areas for improvement across the LASCH which, if addressed, could have a huge positive impact on the outcomes for the YPs.

This section discusses the research process (methodology and methods, along with improvements), conclusions and recommendations for the future.

6.1 Revisiting the Research Proposal

The initial idea behind this research project was to focus in on the delivery of science in LASCHs. However, it became apparent very early on that there were strategic and operational issues around education in this environment that needed to be understood and addressed before identifying how to improve the teaching of science. Therefore the scope of the project widened to include an understanding of policies and the differences between LASCHs and their education departments as well as the delivery of effective science lessons.

Figure 8: Factors Influencing the Teaching of Science in LASCHs

Figure 8 shows all the different areas that effective science teaching depends on. The Government has made the decision to reduce the number of young offenders that are detained and that education is key in their rehabilitation. A consequence of this is, that while the number of YPs being detain is less, the challenges around behaviour are changing and becoming more difficult. These changes in policy require appropriate funding and monitoring to be in place to ensure they are delivered.

At an institutional level a clear vision on how to rehabilitate rather than punish the young offenders needs to be developed and shared. The increase in older children with more challenging behaviour and the complications of differing lengths of sentences creates 'a series of problems for those charged with

educating young people in custody' (Stephenson, 2007, p.137). All this needs to be taken into consideration when developing a vision to enable the appropriate allocation of resources for staff training and facilities.

When Government policy and institutional vision are aligned and effectively support education, then the barriers to education that an individual YP has, can be addressed. This is for all subjects taught at the unit. Once all these are in place then, the barriers to effective science teaching can be addressed.

6.2 Reviewing the Research Aims and Objectives

As the project widened from the original proposal, but mainly because HoE were interested in the project and influenced the content of the questionnaire, it was imperative that I remained focused on the objectives. I had to refer back to them regularly to keep the research on track.

The aim of this project was to identify best practice in teaching science in LASCHs. To meet this aim the following objectives would need to be met:

1. To understand the difference between the LASCHs
2. To understand the differences between the education departments
3. To identify current practice in science teaching

The project went some way to meeting these objectives. It was not possible, for example, to gain an understanding of the education departments' budget as the HoE do not have a clear view of it themselves. The staffing of the education department in relation to the curriculum delivered was difficult to interpret as the size of the unit had a disproportionate impact on the number and type of educators and how they were deployed. This was analysed to give an overview of curriculum delivered and to identify good practice that could be shared amongst the units.

The difficulties that science teachers were experiencing in delivering their subject in this setting were identified along with good practice, though within the timescale of the project it was not possible to share this information.

6.3 Revisiting the Methodology

I feel that the methodological approach to this research was appropriate as a case study allowed me to gain an holistic view of LASCH while gaining more insight into the constraints of teaching in this setting. That is I gained 'an insight into the context of a problem as well as illustrating the main point' (Fry, Ketteridge and Marshall, cited by Wilson, 2013, p.257) as discussed in section 4.2.

If necessary a case study would have allowed me to change my data collection methods: I did not have to change my methods because:

- 1) the questionnaires enabled me to collect factual data to gain a broad impression of LASCH and the education departments without the need to meet the HoE. This was important because it would not have been possible to meet them given the locations, costs and timescale. (see section 4.3.1).

- 2) The structured interviews meant that the initial contact with my peers was on a 1:1 basis and not in a group interview setting. This meant I was able to start building a rapport with them without the awkwardness of a group interview, especially as it would have been the first time the science teachers would have met each other. It was easier to build rapport over the phone than I anticipated. I believe this is because the teachers had the same desire to improve their practice and wanted to know that they were not alone and others were experiencing the same challenges.

I am confident that both the research methodology and methods were appropriate for this, as I was met with positive reactions from all involved. This was quite daunting at the outset as this was the first time collaborative working had been attempted and I had no indication of how it would be received, but my belief now is that as staff feel isolated working collaboratively is essential in the future.

As I had an 80% response rate from HoE and 100% involvement from the science teachers, I was more concerned about how my bias (O'Leary, 2007) would impact on outcomes than the issues around validity and reliability (Wilson, 2009; Flyvbjerg, 2006) as discussed in section 4.2

If I was re-doing the project I would have met the HoE at the start of the project to discuss the project rather than use my HoE as advocate to build relationships and develop a rapport. I would have been able to judge whether following up queries would be appropriate or not. As a result the analysis is based on factual data and gave no insight into how the HoE think and feel about working in this environment.

Specific improvements to the questionnaires would be:

- Adding a “prefer not to say” or “data not available” option so that I would be confident that all questions had been considered. Some boxes were left empty and I was not sure if they had missed this section or were unable to provide data. I did not want to keep asking them in case it antagonised them (BERA, 2011). I thought that by stating this at the top of the questionnaire that respondents would write this in the space provided.
- Asking HoE about training or relevant experience. For example, if they had worked at an FE college they would be aware of other equivalent qualifications that might be more appropriate for these YPs.
- Asking about progress over a set period of time as suggested by a HoE *‘requires criteria, eg length of stay’*.
- Asking if reading age is ascertained on admission (as it asked for on the eAssesst system).

6.4 Findings and Recommendations

If education or the lack of it is a key risk factor when it comes to offending and re-offending, and, if as Nick Clegg said, education is really seen as giving young offenders the opportunity to change then education needs to be given a higher priority: The education department needs to be effectively monitored against appropriate KPIs. Appendix 11 lists the recommendations from this research.

The current system does not fully focus on the YPs and there needs to be a change in culture to ensure the best possible outcomes for them. Currently, LASCHs work independently and even though there are constraints around how they are run due to number and type of beds, I believe there would be many advantages to them working together and being considered as one school as discussed in some sections below.

6.4.1 Budget

In general there does not appear to be a separate education budget. This suggests education is not seen as a priority by the managers of the LASCH. This is against the understanding that education is key to reducing offending and the philosophy that it is central to a YPs detention. It is separating decision makers from practitioners and means that people who do not fully understand education are ultimately deciding what gets resourced. Without an annual budget it is not possible to effectively plan and deliver a work program. Curriculum based issues (as discussed below) could be overcome by scheduling in specific education days over the year. I believe that this goes hand in hand with not having the correct measures (KPIs) in place for education. Going forward an education budget should be assigned based on previous spend, if the data is available. Giving HoE control over their staff budget means they could decide how to use any under-spend as a result of staff turn-over.

6.4.2 Allowances

I was anecdotally aware that teachers are paid differently between LASCH and in some instances within LASCH. I believe the education department within a LASCH is a 'special school' (DfE, 2014a, p.26) and therefore the teachers are entitled to an SEN allowance. Even if the education department is not designated as a special school the teachers' pay and conditions should be the same and not locally agreed. This must be in line with the guidance outlined in 'School teachers' pay and conditions document 2014 and guidance on school teachers' pay and Conditions'

If a recommendation to see education within the LASCHs as one school then there would be consistency over pay. This may provide the opportunity a head of subject within the sector, allowing for progression which currently does not exist.

6.4.3 Curriculum Provision

This is perhaps the key area for LASCHs, and it ties in with Stephenson's (2007, p.134) question 'what is the purpose of education in a LASCH or any custodial institution?' In general the core curriculum is not being delivered, for many different and valid reasons, but does this matter? If it does, could it be delivered in more innovative ways? For example the average length of stay is between 3 and 7 months so could regular "Careers days" or "Citizenship days" be organised and delivered. Section 5.2.6, details some practices already utilised that could be implemented across the sector, for example, training care staff to deliver SRE and a careers afternoon every other week.

What is clear from this research is that the YPs usually have low levels of literacy (section 3.1.5) and the curriculum needs to address this. A KPI based on improving literacy skills should be implemented and monitored.

6.4.4 Occupancy

The occupancy level of the units which replied varied from 85-99%. This is not in line with the figures issued by the DfE which stated '77% Occupancy at 31 March 2014' (ibid, 2014, p.1). While I accept that I was looking at academic year and the report implies financial year, I would not expect the figures to be so different. It could be because only 5 units were prepared or able to share this data that it is so different. If occupancy rates are used in decision making processes, then the figure needs to be robust and reliable.

6.4.5 Qualifications and Training of Education Staff

The training that staff undergo will depend on the LASCH's vision and the education department's priorities (see 6.4.3). Once this is identified then a skills gap analysis can be carried out to identify training needs.

However, it is already known that these YPs have high incidents of mental health problems (see section 3.6.1), poor literacy and numeracy skills (see section 3.1.5) and are recognised as the most difficult and traumatised children in the country. It would make sense to invest in the specialist training of education staff to deal with these issues especially as strong teacher-pupil relationships are key to engaging them; the more able the staff are at understanding with them the quicker

the relationships can be built. This would help mitigate some of the issues around YPs being put straight into education as staff will feel more confident in dealing with them. This training could be part of an induction program or joint LASCH INSET days.

With the smaller units, consideration should be given to training staff to teach more than one subject. This means that core subjects would be covered. If this model was extended to the larger units then core subjects might be covered even when staff leave. This depends on decisions made on curriculum provided.

As the YPs are mostly of secondary school age with the NC level 3, should LASCH have a mixture of secondary and primary trained teachers? This would help to overcome the vast range of previous attainment. Primary trained staff are better qualified to teach reading and could provide training to other teachers on how to do this.

Looking longer-term and as there is an increase in EAL pupils in mainstream schools it would make sense to train staff for this. Lesson delivered for EAL pupils can help those with low levels in literacy and young reading age.

If a gap analysis is to be carried out to identify the skills shortages then consideration could also be given to training care staff to deliver some curriculum topics such as SRE, which already happens in one unit.

6.4.6 Class Size

The KPI on class size needs to be better understood. It clearly states that the ratio of teachers to YPs should be 1:4, but in some classes it is as high as 1:6. An additional member of staff is present, but it is not a teacher. Clarity needs to sort as to what this KPI is trying to achieve. Whatever the answer is, a better understanding of how these lessons are organised is needed before best practice can be shared.

If it is acceptable to have 6 YPs in a class with an additional member of staff the role of this person need clarifying. Are they present to manage behaviour or act as a TA?

If it is not acceptable then as a matter of urgency the ratio of teachers to YPs need to be addressed.

6.4.7 Assessment and Progression

What and how assessments are carried out vary greatly. With re-offending rates as high as 71%, (MoJ, 2014, p.3), a consistent approach to assessing progress would reduce YPs having no data on re-admission to the system giving a more accurate picture of the individual and their progress. This is another advantage of operating as one education department as a joint decision on the appropriate assessment tool would be made. It may even make economic sense as one system rather than many are being purchased (economies of scale). A decision on what to assess needs to be made.

As the YPs have undiagnosed problems it would be advantageous to carry out a full educational assessment to understand their full educational needs and not just their attainment. This lack of understanding of a YP's needs is in line with Stephenson's (2007, p.137) findings that YPs leave detention without anything assembling a full educational assessment.

Yet in the short time they are detained a full assessment by an educational psychologist is not given a high enough priority to ensure it happens. This would help current teaching staff, as well as those in their next educational setting. This would be in line with the new SEND Code of Practice and the development of a EHC Plan. When a YP enters the secure estate money should come from their LA. The YPs are still being let down if the opportunity to fully assess them while they are detained is not taken.

It is good that educational progression occurs in secure units and given their length of stay the progression made is excellent. This may simply be down to the simple fact that it is very difficult for the YPs to avoid going to school in this setting.

As stated previously the aim of detention of young offenders is to get them to 'contribute positively to society in adult life' (MoJ, 2014, p.3). The YPs are usually of school age, so for them the first step is getting them back into school.

This means ensuring that while detained a full assessment of their needs is carried out that can be shared with their next school.

6.4.8 SEN/ESBD

As discussed in 3.1.3 above many YPs come into the secure setting with little or no previous educational assessment. Just because they do not have a statement of SEN it does not mean that they do not have a SEN. They are described as 'extremely vulnerable children with most complex and challenging needs' (Ofsted 2012) and 'violent', with 'mental health issues and sexual exploitation' on the increase, on top of previously identified issues of 'poor educational attainment, dysfunctional family backgrounds, and drug and alcohol related dependency' (YJB 2014).

This supports my belief that for whatever reason they are detained that all of the YPs have a special need on top of those recognised in the usual scheme of things (dyslexia, dyspraxia, ASD, ADHD etc). If the extent of SEN/ESBD is not fully understood, does this explain the lack of additional support in lessons?

6.4.9 Support in Lessons

This ties in with SEN/ESBD as discussed above. Before appropriate support can be provided for the YP in a lesson, their educational and emotional needs must be understood. There needs to be transparency over how it is decided and who needs it. Clear criteria could be put in place based on numeracy and literacy levels and safety.

6.5 Science

This section looks at the specific issues related to teaching science in this setting.

6.5.1 Training

Mount (1997, p.39) found 40% of teachers were trained to teach science, the situation is slightly better in LASCH as 50% are qualified secondary science teachers. But this does raise concerns over the training required to ensure safe and suitable lessons are delivered.

With only 50% of the teachers having had H&S training as part of their PGCE and a lack of clarity over whether there is a science H&S policy and if there is, who has responsibility for it then H&S training should be carried out. This will ensure that the teachers are compliant with H&S regulations. A risk assessment proforma should be used when practical lessons are carried out taking into account the challenges of specific YPs as well as the risks of the practical.

50% of the science teachers are teaching outside their specialism, me included. This means the Ofsted recommendation in the Maintaining Curiosity Report that 'subject-specific continuing professional development for subject leaders and teachers that improves the quality of assessment and feedback for pupils in science' (Ibid, 2013 p.7) should be implemented and monitored to make sure happens.

6.5.2 Equipment

As Stephenson's (2007) found laboratories and poorly equipped (Ibid, p.132). This is supported by my research as some units do not have any means of doing practicals. Those that do have a laboratory have concerns over identifying and purchasing equipment including not having the time to do it, where to purchase it from and buying small enough quantities. Again if the education departments are seen as one school, equipment could be centrally sourced and divided up between the LASCHs. This would provide economies of scale and possible make equipment available to the smaller units which otherwise might find it too costly (see section 3.2.4).

Even though there is no education budget and therefore no science budget, no one had any issues with purchasing equipment if they could make a sound business case for it.

In contradiction to Stephenson's findings that staff tend to have access to IT (see section 3.2.4) the availability varied at each LASCH varied. Control over internet access by the YPs was not consistent and there is a clear need to implement good software to manage this. Where staff had access to the internet they found it invaluable.

Access to good IT, not just for the YPs, but also the teaching staff, is essential to helping YPs get back on track. It will facilitate assessment, learning and qualifications as so many are now available on-line. Implementation of working IT systems as soon as is practicable would have an immediate positive impact on teaching and learning.

6.5.3 Lesson Planning

All teachers identified lessons that were successful in this setting, with some overlap. These lessons could be shared today to help build a bank of resources that all teachers can use.

Once decisions on the appropriate curriculum and qualifications for the YPs are made (potentially by a Head of Science in LASCH) joint development of lesson plans and schemes of work could be delivered.

6.6 Dissemination of Findings

It was hoped that the findings and recommendations from this project would be presented to the participants within the timescale of the project but unfortunately this did not happen. This was due to the SANed meetings being cancelled and LASCH not having the budget for the science teachers to get together. I have managed to secure a £1000 Santander Bursary to disseminate my findings and a meeting is scheduled for June after the GCSE exams.

I am hoping that the recommendation from this project will be implemented as they will go some way to meet the chairs of the YJB, Lord McNally's (2014) belief that 'we need to address new issues, embrace new ideas, and find better and more efficient ways of working together.'

Appendix 1: Local Authority Secure Children's Home

Name	Location
Aldine House	Sheffield
Atkinson	Devon
Aycliffe	Durham
Barton Moss	Manchester
Beechfield	West Sussex
Clare Lodge	Peterborough
Clayfields	Nottingham
East More	Leeds
Hillside	South Wales
Kyloe House	Northumberland
Lansdowne	East Sussex
Lincolnshire	Lincolnshire
St Catherine's	Merseyside
Swanwick	Southampton
Vinney Green	Bristol

Appendix 2: Key Performance Indicators

A	Staff Management and Training
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Staff numbers on shift comply at all times with minimum standard required by Ofsted Care 1:3 Teachers 1:4 2. % of total WTE care and teaching staff complement with more than one year's relevant experience 3. % of total WTE care staff with NVQ level 3 or equivalent professional qualification 4. % of total WTE care staff and teaching staff who have completed their induction training within one month of commencement
B	Assessment and Training Plans
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First reviews are satisfactorily conducted within one month of Planning Meeting 2. Risk management plan for inclusion in first review is satisfactorily completed
C	Ethos Culture and Care
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. % total of WTE care and teaching staff who are trained to appropriate level in physical restrictive intervention techniques 2. Records of incidents of physical restraint are maintained 3. Records of incidents of single separation are maintained 4. Complaints are received and pursued in compliance with service specification 5. % of WTE care and teaching staff trained in recognition of abuse 6. Suicide and self risk screening conducted upon admission
D	Outside Contacts
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Weekly visits by representative from VOICE achieved 2. Monthly visits by Quality Reviewing Officer (Reg 33) achieved
E	Enriched Activities & Offending Behaviour
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Average of 12 hours enriched activities per week per young person achieved 2. Average of 1 hour key working per week per young person achieved
F	Healthcare and Physical Wellbeing
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Exit medical within 5 working days for sentenced young people
G	Premises Security & Safety
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Security maintained (i.e. no absconsions whilst on mobility) 2. Adequate safety/emergency drills to regulation standard are carried out 3. % of total WTE care and teaching and support staff proven to have completed fire safety and critical incident response training within one month of commencement 4. All rooms available for occupancy
H	Service Management
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Referrals are accepted within scope of contract 2. Placements continue without breakdown

Appendix 3: Questionnaire to Heads of Education

About the Unit:

The following questions are about size and type of unit.

I have looked at your websites to try and ascertain exact bed number information and I was not sure if the numbers were for 2013-14 or 2014-15. Please could you complete and where necessary amend the data for your unit only?

Secure Unit	Number of beds: 2012-13	Number of beds: 2013-14	Signature and name of Head of Education
Aldine House Secure Children's Centre	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB: 8	
Atkinson Secure Children's Home	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB: 0	
Aycliffe Secure Services	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB: 24	
Barton Moss	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB: 24	
Beechfield Secure Unit	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: 7 YJB: 0	
Clare Lodge Secure Unit	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: 0 Female: 16 Welfare: 16 YJB: 0	
Clayfields House Secure Unit	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB: 14	
East Moor Secure Children's Centre	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: 0 Welfare: YJB: 22	
Hillside Secure Centre	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB: 10	

Secure Unit	Number of beds: 2012-13	Number of beds: 2013-14	Signature and name of Head of Education
Kyloe House Secure Children's Home	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: 12 YJB: 0	
Lansdowne Secure Unit	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: 7 YJB: 0	
Leverton Secure Unit	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: 16 YJB: 0	
Lincolnshire Secure Unit	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB: 11	
Red Bank Community Home	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	
St Catherine's Secure Centre	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	
Swanwick Lodge	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB:	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB: 4	
Vinney Green Secure Unit	Male: 16 Female: 8 Welfare: 3 YJB: 21	Male: Female: Welfare: YJB: 24	
1) What is the average length of stay for a young person? (in days)			
2) Over the last year what was the average percent occupancy?			
3) What is the average of the young people on admission?			

About the Education Department:

The following questions are about size of the education department and the type of education provision available. If you are unable to answer a question please state **data is unavailable**, if you prefer not to answer a question please state **prefer not to answer** as this is your right under BERA guidelines 2011.

1) As the Head of Education are you a qualified teacher? If yes, please circle the correct answer Secondary Primary Other please specify	Yes / No
2) How much teaching (if any) do you do? (please state how many lessons you teach out of the maximum number over the week)	
3) How many of the following do you employ? Please use full time equivalents (FTEs) a. qualified teachers b. instructors/unqualified teachers c. teaching assistants/learning support assistants d. higher level teaching assistants	FTE
4) Would you be prepared to share your last Ofsted report?	Yes / No
5) Please complete the table below indicating the number (as FTEs) and type of staff that teach each subject. Please also indicate if support staff are present in the lessons.	
(list of subjects taken from https://www.gov.uk/national-curriculum/key-stage-3-4)	

Subject	Qualified teacher	Non-qualified teacher	Instructor	TA or other support
English				
Mathematics				
Science Biology Chemistry Physics				
Information and communication technology				
Design and technology				
Art and design				
Home economics				

Humanities Geography History RE				
MFL French Spanish German Other				
Music				
Physical Education				
Citizenship				
Sex and Relationship education				
Careers education				
Vocational subjects Hair and Beauty Car Mechanics Car body work Agriculture and Horticulture Other (please specify)				

6) How do you assess the young person's NC levels?	
7) When do you assess the young person's NC levels?	
8) What is the average NC level on arrival in a. Literacy b. Numeracy c. Science	
9) What is the average NC level on leaving in a. Literacy b. Numeracy c. Science	
10) What is the maximum class size?	

11)Over the year 2013/14 what were the number of pupils with statements for a. SEN? b. ESB? c. EAL?	
12)What was the total number of young people in your unit in the year 2013/14?	
13)What was your education budget for 2013/14?	
14)What is your education budget for 2014/15?	
15)Does the education department stick to the local authority term dates?	Yes / No
If, no then please state the number of weeks that the education department is operational during the academic year as well as any pattern if there is one. (e.g. 6 weeks of education 2 weeks off)	
16)Which of the following allowances do the education team receive? a) Secure unit allowance b) Community homes allowance c) Special education needs (SEN) d) Teaching and learning responsibility TLR)	

About Science:

The following questions are about the resources available to the science teacher. If you are unable to answer a question please state **data is unavailable**, if you prefer not to answer a question please state **prefer not to answer** as this is your right under BERA guidelines 2011.

1) How long has your unit been teaching science?	
2) Do you have laboratory facilities?	
3) What was your actual spend on science in 2013/14?	
4) What is your budget for science in 2014/15?	

5) Has the budget remained the same over the last 2-3 years? ($\pm 5\%$)	
6) How long has your current science teacher been in post?	

Thank you for taking the time to complete the questionnaire. Please could I have your contact details (email and/or work contact number) in case there is anything I need to clarify.

If there is anything you would like to add please use the space below.

Appendix 4: Structure Interview Questions to Teachers

About You:

What subject did you do your degree in?	
Do you have a PGCE? If yes in what subject?	
Do you have QTS?	
How long have you been teaching science for?	
How long have you been teaching science in a secure unit?	
Have you received any specific training for YPs with: Dyslexia? Low levels in literacy? Low levels in numeracy? BESD? Other (please specify)? Was this training in your current post or previous post?	
How useful was this training for teaching in your current post?	
What training have you attended since being in post? Which ones would you recommend to other science teachers in the secure setting?	
How do you overcome the issues of poor literacy	

<p>numeracy</p> <p>Challenging behaviour</p>	
<p>Have you received any training for health and safety in a science practical lesson? (as a technician or head of science) Please specify</p>	
<p>How useful was this training for teaching in your current post?</p>	
<p>Have you had any CLEAPPs training?</p>	
<p>Are you members of CLEAPPS?</p>	
<p>How useful was this training for teaching in your current post?</p>	
<p>Where do you get your lesson ideas from?</p>	
<p>Do you have any links with other schools? Universities? Pupil Referral Units? Local authorities?</p>	
<p>How useful is this for teaching in your current post?</p>	

Lesson configuration:

The following questions are about development and structure of lessons. If you are unable to answer a question please state **data is unavailable**, if you prefer not to answer a question please state **prefer not to answer** as this is your right under BERA guidelines 2011. Please remember all your answers are confidential and your responses will be anonymous. If a question is not relevant to your setting please state **N/A** so that I know you have considered the question.

1) Do you have a health and safety policy for science?	Yes / no
If yes a) who is responsible for writing it?	You / HoE / H&S officer / other (please specify)
b) who is responsible for updating it?	You / HoE / H&S officer / other (please specify)
c) how frequently is it reviewed?	Annually
2) Do you have a standard risk assessment proforma for practical lessons?	
3) Do you use a lesson plan proforma for lessons?	
4) How useful are these in delivering safe lesson?	
5) How are new YPs introduced into practical lessons?	
6) How do the YPs feel about science?	
7) What is the balance between chemistry, physics and biology?	
Explore this in relation to numeracy, literacy and poor behaviour.	

<p>8) Have you any lessons that have always worked with the YPs?</p> <p>If yes, please explain.</p> <p>Would you be prepared to share this with other science teachers in the secure setting?</p> <p>Would you be happy for them to trial them and give feedback on how they went? (remember that one of the aims of the project is to identify and share best practice)</p>	
<p>9) What would you say are your best 3/4 lessons?</p> <p>Would you be prepared to share this with other science teachers in the secure setting?</p> <p>Would you be happy for them to trial them and give feedback on how they went?</p>	
10)Do the YPs have access to the internet during lessons?	
11)Do you have access to the internet during lessons?	
12)Do you use science apps and games during lessons?	
13)How useful are these in delivering interesting lesson? How do you prevent YPs having open access to the internet?	
14)What is the maximum number of YPs in a lesson?	
15)Do you have TA support in lessons? Theory lessons? Practical lessons?	

16)Do you have technician support to prepare practical lessons?	
17)Who do you order your equipment from?	
18)Who orders the equipment?	
19)Do you have any issues with finding and buying equipment?	
20)How many lessons do you teach a week?	
21)How many PPAs do you have a week?	
22)Do you get additional time to prepare and clear up after practicals?	
23)Do you follow a National Curriculum Scheme of work? If not why not?	
24)Have you developed your own SoW? Would you be prepared to share it? And receive feedback on it?	
25)What cross curricula teaching are you involved in?	

If you are prepared to share any of the documents above please could you email them to me at rona.chellew@southglos.gov.uk

About Science Qualification:

The following questions are about the qualifications you deliver. If you are unable to answer a question please state **data is unavailable**, if you prefer not to answer a question please state **prefer not to answer** as this is your right under BERA guidelines 2011. Please remember all your answers are confidential and your responses will be anonymous.

Which (if any) of the following qualifications do you deliver?

Qualification	Exam Board
BTEC Science	
GCSE	
apt awards	
AQA certificates	
iGCSE: Biology Chemistry Physics	
Entry level science	
Other (please specify)	
Why are these qualifications suitable for the YPs you teach?	

Please give details of grades achieved:

Qualification	Grades achieved 2012	Grades achieved 2013
BTEC Science		
GCSE		
apt awards		
AQA certificates		
iGCSE: Biology Chemistry Physics		
Entry level science		
Other (please specify)		

Miscellaneous Questions

	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Very dissatisfied
	1	2	3	4
How happy are you with the level of support you have in your job?				
How happy are you in your job?				
How happy are you with the progress a YP makes in science?				
How happy are you with the suitability of the lessons for the YPs?				
How happy are you with the training provided to teach in this setting?				
How happy are you with your level of knowledge to teach YPs with ESB/D/SEN/D?				
Is there anything you would like to add/include in this project?				
<p>Would you be willing to attend a meeting in October with the participants of this project? I will feedback the outcome of my findings and it will be an opportunity to meet peers and discuss a way forward with the outcomes.</p> <p>Available dates</p>				

Appendix 5: Permission Letter To Head of Education

Dear ,

I am writing to you to gain permission to conduct a case study to identify best practice in teaching science in secure units. This research is for my dissertation module of my MA in Education.

The aim of my research is to identify and formulate a dissemination approach for best practice in the delivery of science in secure units. Specifically, I am planning to try and identify and share best practice in

- the safe use of practicals
- overcoming literacy and numeracy challenges
- making decisions on the relevance/appropriateness of qualifications for individual pupils
- developing engaging, relevant and interesting teaching materials within the curriculum.

The duration of the study will be approximately one year. Participation by my peers will be voluntary and conducted in accordance with BERA guidelines (2011) ensuring confidentiality and anonymity. At this early stage it is anticipated that their involvement will be the completion of a questionnaire with a follow up meeting to disseminating findings by the end of the 2014/15 financial year.

As the community of practitioners in the sector is small and stretched, I believe this project has the potential to benefit both individual science teachers and the collective community, through the efficiencies of sharing what works rather than re-inventing and focusing on practical outputs, application and outcomes rather than theory.

If you wish to discuss the project in more detail please do not hesitate to ask. If you are happy with the project to go ahead please can you sign the bottom of this letter?

Yours sincerely,

Appendix 6: Consent Letter to Head of Education

Dear ,

I am writing to you to gain permission to conduct a case study to identify best practice in teaching science in secure units. This research is for my dissertation module of my MA in Education.

The aim of my research is to identify and formulate a dissemination approach for best practice in the delivery of science in secure units. Specifically, I am planning to try and identify and share best practice in

- the safe use of practicals
- overcoming literacy and numeracy challenges
- making decisions on the relevance/appropriateness of qualifications for individual pupils
- developing engaging, relevant and interesting teaching materials within the curriculum.

The duration of the study will be approximately one year. Participation by my peers will be voluntary and conducted in accordance with BERA guidelines (2011) ensuring confidentiality and anonymity. At this early stage it is anticipated that their involvement will be the completion of a questionnaire with a follow up meeting to disseminating findings by the end of the 2014/15 financial year.

As the community of practitioners in the sector is small and stretched, I believe this project has the potential to benefit both individual science teachers and the collective community, through the efficiencies of sharing what works rather than re-inventing and focusing on practical outputs, application and outcomes rather than theory.

If you wish to discuss the project in more detail please do not hesitate to ask. If you are happy with the project to go ahead please can you sign the bottom of this letter?

Yours sincerely,

Appendix 7: Consent Letter to Participants

As part of my MA Education I would like to identify and share best practice in teaching science in secure units. In order to do this I would appreciate it if you could complete the attached questionnaire that covers

- the safe use of practicals
- literacy and numeracy challenges
- the relevance/appropriateness of qualifications
- developing resources within the curriculum

The majority of work will be carried out by me as a co-participant as this project will form the basis for my dissertation. It has the potential to benefit us as individual science teachers and as a community, through the efficiencies of sharing and focusing on practical outputs rather than theory.

Your participation in the project will be conducted in accordance with BERA guidelines (2011). This means that:

- Your involvement is voluntary
- You can choose not to answer specific questions
- You are assured confidentiality and anonymity unless you wish to be identified

Storage and use of the data will adhere to the Data Protection Act 1998.

Once I have analysed the data we will have a follow up meeting to discuss the findings and how we can implement best practice in science teaching in secure units.

If you have any questions please do not hesitate to contact me, my email address is [contact details removed]

Please sign below if you agree to be part of this project looking at teaching science in this unique setting

Participant signature..... Print name.....

Appendix 8 (Public Version): Summary of Findings – Heads of Education

Ethics note: In the public version, detailed individual-level responses have been removed to protect participant anonymity. This appendix presents aggregated themes from the Head of Education questionnaires.

Theme	Key Points Reported by Heads of Education	Frequency (out of 12)
Unit Operations	Significant variation in size, occupancy, and proportion of welfare vs YJB beds.	High
Curriculum	Core subjects always delivered; vocational/arts varied between units.	High
Staffing & Training	Qualifications generally high, but limited CPD opportunities; reliance on multi-role teaching staff.	Moderate
Assessment	Inconsistent baseline testing; literacy/numeracy assessed but science rarely.	High
Special Educational Needs (SEN)	High prevalence of SEN/ESBD; approaches inconsistent across units.	High
Resources & Budget	Funding varied, resource constraints frequently mentioned.	Moderate
Behaviour Management	Small class sizes essential; group composition influenced learning dynamics.	High

Assessment

Graph showing % of Young People with Statement

Appendix 9 (Public Version): Summary of Findings – Science Teachers

Note: In the public version, detailed interview transcripts have been removed to protect participant anonymity. This appendix presents aggregated themes emerging from structured interviews with seven science teachers.

Theme	Key Points Reported by Science Teachers	Frequency (out of 7)
Teaching Challenges	Low literacy and numeracy levels; difficulty linking science to YPs' lives.	High
Practical Science	Strong desire to use practicals, but restrictions due to behaviour and safety risks.	High
Resources	Lack of fully equipped laboratories; improvisation common.	High
Curriculum & Planning	Need for flexible schemes of work; short sentences disrupt continuity.	High
Qualifications	Mixed provision; some GCSE entries but concerns about appropriateness.	Moderate
SEN & ESBD	Teachers often unsupported in addressing complex needs; training gaps highlighted.	High
Support & Collaboration	Feelings of professional isolation; interest in shared practice across units.	High

Appendix 10 Public Version: Email from Department of Education

In the original dissertation this appendix reproduced email correspondence from the Department for Education. For the purposes of this public version, and to protect staff identities, this appendix has been removed. The relevant content is already summarised in the main body of the dissertation.

Appendix 11: Recommendations from the Research

1	HoE to have control over non-staff and staff education budget
2	HoE to work together and with the teachers' unions to ensure the correct allowances are paid to teachers in all LASCH across England and Wales to ensure consistency.
3	HoE to identify the advantages and disadvantages of operating as one education department with in LASCH.
4	HoE and teaching staff to identify the most appropriate curriculum for YPs
5	HoE to ascertain if occupancy rates are calculated using the same method and understand why the figures are so different. Identify what it is used for.
6	Train education staff in how to deal with mental health issues.
7	Train education staff in how to improve literacy and numeracy skills through their subject.
8	HoE to gain clarity over the KPI and implement changes if required.
9	Investigate the advantages of using the same assessment tool (cost, tracking progression).
10	Identify and implement the best assessment tool.
11	Look at average reading age of YPs on admission.
12	Identify and recommend KPI for education.
13	Full educational assessment to be part of KPI
14	Develop clear criteria for providing support in lessons.
15	H&S training to be given to all science teachers.
16	Ensure a H&S Policy for science teaching is available and implemented (including a risk assessment proforma).
17	ensure science teachers continued professional development is delivered
18	Investigate the possibility of having a central purchasing system for laboratory equipment.
19	Identify and implement software packages to monitor and manage internet access for teachers and YPs.

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